
RISING INNOVATION & EMERGING TALENTS

WRITTEN AND
PUBLISHED BY

RISING INNOVATION AND EMERGING TALENTS FROM THE EAST

White Paper on startup ecosystems, innovation and talents focusing on EASA* countries supplemented by Kyrgyzstan

Prepared by **MeOut Group**
(*Euro-Asian Startup Awards)

Edited and written by Sándor Nagy PhD

Our Community

MeOut Group has been focusing on education and innovation in the past decade. From the operational headquarter (Budapest, Hungary) through the many activities, MeOut has a wide reach of regions including: The Visegrad 4 Countries (Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Czech Republic), Western-Balkan (North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Albania, Kosovo, Bosnia and Herzegovina), The Caucasus (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia), The Turkic Council States – in which Hungary is being present as an observer state, and Central Asia (Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan).

MeOut Group's main activities involve organising hackathons (HackMeOut), ideathons (ChallengeMeOut) and other events focusing on youth, innovation and startup ecosystem. MeOut is also the founding body of the Euro-Asian Startup Awards (EASA). The desirable goal of these activities is to foster regional and local ecosystem development.

This research was conducted with the involvement of local startups, incubators, accelerators, hubs, investors, venture capitalists and other ecosystem players.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

4	1. INTRODUCTION
6	2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND
8	2.1 STARTUPS, ECOSYSTEMS AND INNOVATION HUBS
11	2.2 ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPACTS OF STARTUPS
14	2.3 SOME ISSUES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STARTUP ECOSYSTEMS
18	3. FOCUS OF OUR STUDY
20	4. COUNTRY BY-COUNTRY ECOSYSTEM OVERVIEW
22	4.1 ARMENIA (ARM)
29	4.2 AZERBAIJAN (AZE)
36	4.3 BELARUS (BLR)
44	4.4 GEORGIA (GEO)
51	4.5 KAZAKHSTAN (KAZ)
58	4.6 KYRGYZSTAN (KGZ)
65	4.7 MOLDOVA (MDA)
72	4.8 RUSSIA (RUS)
81	4.9 TURKEY (TUR)
89	4.10 UKRAINE (UKR)
97	4.11 UZBEKISTAN (UZB)
104	5. OUR PRIMARY RESEARCH
105	5.1 APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY
109	5.2 REGIONAL OUTLOOK
116	6. KEY RESULTS & TAKEAWAYS
117	6.1 TALENTS
122	6.2 ECOSYSTEM
125	6.3 MARKET PRESENCE AND THE GLOBAL EXPANSION
128	6.4 CHALLENGES
132	7. INTERVIEWS
132	7.1 ADVICERA (UKR)
135	7.2 GENERATIONS (RUS)
138	7.3 IBA INNOVATION CENTER (AZE)
143	7.4 MTS STARTUP HUB (RUS)
146	7.5 OPEN DATA INCUBATOR (UKR)
147	7.6 TRANGELS (TUR)
154	7.7 UKRAINIAN STARTUP FUND (UKR)
157	SUMMARY
159	CONTRIBUTORS
161	REFERENCES

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

INTRODUCTION

1. INTRODUCTION

This research was designed to present our network, which we have built up over many years of work, from a very special perspective. We make our day-to-day efforts to contribute to the development of startup ecosystems. We believe that together with our partners we can achieve this goal even more effectively and successfully.

This White Paper provides an initial snapshot that will form the basis of our further strategy and innovative ideas. Our research work focuses on the EASA region and 1 additional promising country: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Russia, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan and 1 additional country, Kyrgyzstan.

In the course of the research, we did not aim to explore the startup ecosystems of the given countries in a perfect and far-reaching way, as this would have been limited by serious temporal and methodological constraints. We sought to analyze countries in the given region using factors considered important and decisive for a conscious and intelligent ecosystem development. These factors include talents, qualified workforce, startups and ecosystems, innovation, elements of a supportive environment and the potential for global expansion.

We recommend this White Paper to all interested parties, investors, ecosystem developers, academic researchers and our stakeholders.

We would also like to thank our partners, interviewees and respondents for their contribution to the success of this research.

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

**THEORETICAL
BACKGROUND**

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The term *adaptive pressure* means that it is essential to react to external environmental or even internal, organizational changes, and this response should be as intelligent as possible. The essence of this is to be able to follow a successful long-term adaptation path based on quality information, with the right knowledge and skills. An important component of these processes is the development of innovation activities and learning skills. Ignoring or neglecting reactions – in this context – narrows the possibilities of the given entity, and eventually they can cause its termination.

It is no different in socio-economic systems, including individual actors and higher levels of organization. Think of cities, regions, countries, but also spatial or virtual concentrations of economic activity: corporate collaborations, clusters, innovation networks, startup ecosystems. Nowadays, a number of circumstances and factors emerge or are just suddenly appreciating that underline the importance of these intelligent responses.

Innovation is not just a buzzword, but one of the keys to our sustainable future. Responsible, technology-focused innovation serves not only the return on capital, but also the interests of the natural environment and society at macro level. The question is whether innovation is a must, an opportunity or a precondition for survival? In our view, the truth is rather close to the latter.

In today's globalized world, startups are at the forefront of such innovations. Through their new value propositions, they promote technological transformation, the completion of information processes, the activation of known and hidden resources, and the efficient use of resources, which ultimately also contributes to the management of sustainability.

2.1 STARTUPS, ECOSYSTEMS AND INNOVATION HUBS

A *startup* is not just a starting company and should not be confused with a beginner SME.

A “startup” is more of an attitude, a mindset, a commitment to innovation, embodied in a special organization, which is also served by the special support environment. The latter is called the technology innovation startup ecosystem. Startups of this kind can be described by the following characteristics (Nagy, 2020; Wu–Atkinson, 2017):

- the founders are characterized by innovative personality traits, a divergent way of thinking that differs from the average,
- they are characterized by an organizational culture conducive to innovation, progression and growth, which implies openness and high-quality learning skills,
- promote the digital transformation, mainly through the use of digital solutions and technologies,
- special non-traditional resources are activated and utilized (e.g. information, knowledge, creativity, network positions, relationship capital, ecosystem benefits),
- Its innovation activities can induce disruptive processes. All this means that in their own narrower or in other, even non-competing industries, previously existing solutions, business models, jobs become redundant and outdated. Schumpeter (1934) used the term creative destruction for this phenomenon. Anyway, the trend of disruption is getting faster and faster and more effective due to technological development, the transformation of network structures, and in the same time the frequency of its occasional appearance will become increasingly unpredictable,
- their operation and development are characterized by much higher than average business risks, in return they have a much higher value-creating ability and opportunities, they can not only serve local markets through scalability,
- new and specific funding instruments, opportunities and financing actors will appear in order to handle specific risks and potentials,
- typically attract highly skilled workers and, in their growth phase, can already provide their members with significantly higher incomes than a traditional SME,
- it multiplies many more jobs compared to other traditional industries, with 1 startup job in the US indirectly generating 5 other jobs in the economy,

- the startup sector is characterized by significant research and development expenditures,
- its value proposition may be valid in other markets, so the solution it offers to certain consumer problems can be easily transferred. So the rapid growth of the startup can be expected. In this case, we are talking about scalability,
- highly active (formal and informal) relationships with actors in the operational environment are typical,
- openness, individual and organizational learning skills are also above average,

Startups can really grow and develop if they are embedded in a supportive environment that is favorable to them. Such an environment can be called a startup ecosystem.

This symbiosis is particularly significant. An essential feature of startups is their presence in such an ecosystem, and the success of the ecosystem is also fundamentally determined by the activities of startups. If we talk about development and qualitative progress, the same relation can be observed: startup development is inconceivable without considering the ecosystem, and the ecosystem cannot be developed substantially without its elementary components.

Returning to the characteristics of startups, but already examined in the context of ecosystems, we can add the following to the previous list:

- building highly active (formal and informal) relationships with actors in the operational environment,
- innovation is endogenous, creativity and knowledge are the dominant inputs. Value-creating processes are nonlinear in both startups and within ecosystems. It is becoming more and more clear that the precondition for innovation success is active (local) interactions, connectivity, learning abilities and processes (Nagy-Gulyás, 2015),
- information, knowledge and technology, thanks to the underlying structures, can flow, even between different sectors,
- a good idea is not necessarily enough to succeed in the market, it also requires entrepreneurial skills and ecosystem-generated synergies, the latter including access to specialized services, including funding, the potential to attract talented people, the benefits from agglomeration, competition and the balance of cooperation and other local parameters (Nagy, 2020; Wu-Atkinson, 2017).

The term startup ecosystem appeared in the literature around 2005 and its frequency of use is increasing exponentially from year to year. This is also due to the fact that digital transformation is also accelerating in different sectors, bringing new types of businesses and solutions to life (Cukier–Kon, 2018).

Cukier and Kon (2018) define the supportive environment embracing startups as follows: “A startup ecosystem is defined as a well delimited region within a roughly 50 km (or 1 hour travel) distance of people, their startups, and different types of support organizations, and their interactions could create new startups and develop existing ones in a complex adaptive system (Cukier–Kon, 2018: 2).”

The definition harmonizes well with our way of thinking so far. It contains a reference to the territorial concentration of activities and actors, their diversity (heterogeneity, diversity), the non-linear nature of innovation processes and development directions, namely the criteria for success (Hazell, 2017).

The success (performance) of the ecosystem can be measured by the following attributes:

- the increase in the number and market value of startups,
- the strength of entrepreneurial activity,
- the balanced and responsible development of innovation and digital technology,
- the contribution to the general quality of life, to the well-being of the ecosystem,
- and the creation of the greatest possible social impact including the promotion of sustainability.

According to Wu and Atkinson (2017), a well-functioning ecosystem combines the good characteristics of the public and private sectors and is situated at the intersection of their useful, main functions. This is where the top-down, intelligent control and supportive intervention of the government unite with the agile, risk-seeking, growth-oriented, productivity-enhancing private sector that drives dynamism focusing on innovation.

Thus, the government can put pressure on economic actors to correct market failures or achieve equal competition. It can also regulate the private sector and invest in public goods such as the development of scientific research or important processes with limited market potential, costly and risky talent management, and the creation and maintenance of an enabling environment.

At the same time, the government should not create directly (artificially formulated and maintained) markets and restrict the conditions for fair competition. If the public sector wants to intervene effectively in development processes, the decision makers must be aware of the structures and characteristics outlined so far.

2.2 ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPACTS OF STARTUPS

Developing startups, providing them with financial resources, and supporting their operation in a direct and indirect way is not necessarily as spectacular for the average observer as a huge public investment or a financial transfer to a traditional manufacturing company, where resources flow into tangible capital items. The role and beneficial socio-economic impacts of startups and their ecosystems, as well as their concentration in larger cities, namely their hubs, cannot be questioned (BBWA, 2016; Bone et al., 2019; Colombelli et al., 2016; Corl, 2019; Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation, 2016; Ritchie–Swisher, 2018).

The global startup economy, despite the epidemic, continues to generate a huge value of nearly 3 trillion USD (!), which is equivalent to the GDP of the G7 countries (Startup Genome, 2020: 14). This is just a huge numerical value – which is hard to imagine in its own reality – but let's take a closer look, more specifically at the positive impacts that the sector in question is able to produce.

These consequences can be approached and categorized in many ways, we like the Deloitte (2020) methodology the most. Here, the effects on economic growth are examined in relation to different system levels:

(1) Impact at the level of individuals: the entrepreneur / innovator is the basis and driver of the dynamic relationship between innovation and economic growth. Startups and their successes are spreading an entrepreneurial culture by setting a good example, and through scalability, this type of innovative thinking and approach can be extended to other sectors and geographical regions.

(2) Impact at company level: direct and indirect processes are discussed separately here.

(2a) We speak of a direct impact when startups launch new technologies on the market, and due to the perceived disruption in the market, previous solutions may be pushed back and disappear.

Whether it is the failure and/or exit of startups or the crowding-out effect that results in existing companies losing market share and leaving the market. If we look deeper, disruption seems to be the only possible option for startups without abundant financial

resources if they want to break into a market where competitors strongly protect their market territories and are not interested in change at all, or the industry itself is too rigid, based on ancient instincts, and the entry barriers are unreasonably high within a given market structure.

(2b) Indirectly, startups may induce increased competition on the supply side.

This includes all the consequences of competitors' adaptive responses: efficiency gains, accelerating innovation activities, dynamic markets – a shift from incremental to more radical innovations, a wider and more diverse product range, and more efficient needs. Due to spillover processes, additional economic growth may start in a given industry, region or macroeconomy.

(3) Impact at industry level: as companies in the same industry, whether they are startups or classic players, produce very similar products and services, so new knowledge or technology created by startups in order to rise efficiency probably will start to spread and over time different adaptations of this innovation also appear in the processes of other organizations. This increase in productivity is due to the following cases:

1. productivity growth within existing companies (thanks to innovation efforts at company level),
2. an increase in the market share of high-productivity companies (when companies with innovation occupy an increasing share of the total market); and
3. the emergence of startups displacing less productive incumbent firms (creative destruction).

The mechanism of action at the industry level is that there is a kind of reallocation of resources due to the reorganization/change of market shares.

Impact on the whole economy:

As a rule of thumb, improving productivity at the corporate and industry levels also has an impact on macroeconomic growth. However, this macro level is of particular importance, as government decision-makers usually examine the effects of innovation on the economy and society in this context, using indicators derived from statistics: GDP, job creation, cumulative effects, sustainability aspects, etc.

The economic benefits mentioned above, of course, also induce social benefits through higher incomes (Bone et al., 2019; Deloitte, 2020; Westlund-Olsson, 2011). As a result of well-developed decisions, the standard of living may increase significantly

and, at the same time, the quality of the public services provided by the state may move in a positive direction.

The increased room for financial maneuvers, combined with government measures to innovate and improve the innovation environment, can generate additional benefits. However, we must not think solely of the material dimensions. We feel that non-material effects have much more importance and primacy. These effects are often not measurable in financial terms or can only be monetised in a very indirect way, moreover in some cases, they may only have a very long-term economic impact.

Isenberg and Fabre (2014) present such examples in their article. According to their opinion, entrepreneurship has always had a positive and unique impact on communities and society. Great and successful entrepreneurs and innovators have always been and will continue to be the building blocks of societies. Through their activities, jobs are created and philanthropic intent is very often felt through their actions. Startups, their founders and staff can even set an example, recycling their accumulated knowledge into society through mentoring, teaching or other skills development activities. Through their help and contributions, new generations of entrepreneurship and innovation can develop.

If we look at the evolution of ecosystems or their concentration around cities (hubs), we can add the following items to the list (BBWA, 2019; Startup Europe Partnership, 2018; Startups & Places, 2019):

- when a growing and specialized innovation hub is formulating, it could provide high-quality specialized and other general services to the wider public,
- through the development of ecosystem, the innovation system itself could become more and more efficient, which significantly increases the quality of local products and services including the fields of healthcare, education, digital solutions, public administration, public transport etc.,
- there is a strong educational impact on members of society, such as increasing digital skills, raising awareness, etc.,
- the supporting environment also includes smart infrastructural elements, their existence and accessibility are also favorable for society (e.g. realization of the smart city concept, recreational facilities, world-class technologies in the traditional infrastructural elements),
- the number of special internships is increasing, the integration of young professionals into the labor market can be facilitated, and opportunities for the flow of professional knowledge are expanding,

- the image of the city, region or country will be strengthened,
- under the pressure of the growing actors of the ecosystem – let’s ignore the influence of other factors – the government is trying to improve the performance of its innovation-promoting tasks, from which the citizens can benefit (talent management, special educational tasks, more effective integration of market needs into vocational facilitating lifelong learning processes, legislation to keep pace with technological developments, reforming the tax system, etc.),
- strong capacity building initiatives are emerging, either on the part of the state or on the part of the ecosystem, that did not exist or did not dominate before. Demand for lexical knowledge is expected to be replaced by flexible, problem-oriented knowledge elements and competencies that serve innovation needs,
- as a result of the above listed factors, the cultural development of the given community and society is also expected. This more advanced culture will be more likely to select behaviors and ideas that would be detrimental to the community.

As we have seen the development of startups, ecosystems and their hubs has innumerable benefits for the narrower and wider stakeholder environment. In the next chapter, we examine the specifics of these development activities.

2.3 SOME ISSUES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STARTUP ECOSYSTEMS

The success of the development of innovation startup ecosystems, as well as the economic benefits and positive social impacts mentioned above, can only be achieved if we are aware of the underlying structure, the relevant success factors and the non-linear nature of value-creating, innovation processes. This, of course, requires a new approach and tools from developers and decision makers.

In order to see practical aspects as well as gain deeper insight, it is worth studying Startup Genome’s annual reports on the state of the global startup ecosystem. The latest, highly detailed and highly professional publication builds on a database of more than 1.27 million companies, more than 250 ecosystems and more than 10,000 startup CEOs. Most of these are base on secondary sources, but their primary collection also covers more than 100 experts and approximately 10,000 startups (*note: there is, of course, a common, extensive intersection between the two similar categories, but they do not completely overlap each other*) (Startup Genome, 2020).

For the basic characterization of ecosystems, 4 factors can be mentioned here:

(1) *size/number of elements:*

This factor has already appeared in Porter's (2011) study of industry clusters (agglomerations). He concluded that the increase in membership (number of actors) is strongly related to the increase in productivity and innovation, and even has a positive effect on new entrants. Research of Startup Genome (2019) shows a slightly different picture. There is evidence that average productivity does not increase in relation to size, but the phenomenon of growth orientation can also be detected in ecosystems. The difference between clusters and ecosystems was explained by Cukier and Kon with different system dynamics, the former seems to be more static with permanent relationships, while the latter is seen as a set where actors develop together, helping each other. Ecosystems are treated/considered as a higher-level set/category of which the cluster is a smaller component (Cukier-Kon, 2018 quotes Moore, 1993).

(2) *local relationship structure, embeddedness:* previous researches have already confirmed the beneficial role of local knowledge networks and other embeddedness in relation to growth and development. This factor reveals how closely the startup community is intertwined (linked together) to promote knowledge flow.

(3) *global connectivity:* the content of this factor covers the extent to which a given ecosystem has the potential to engage in the global markets. A higher level of global connectivity helps startups build active relationships with actors in other ecosystems and other entities, thereby raising their own level of performance.

(4) *growth orientation:* growth orientation is one of the basic characteristics and success factors of startups. This factor is directly related to the previous factor. A startup – developing in a globally networked ecosystem – is much more likely to grow and build capacities & skills with the help of such a knowledge which could promote scaling.

In addition to the basic characteristics that describe a given ecosystem, it is also worth looking at the success factors. The Startup Genome (2020) study considers nine success factors influencing performance in ranking different ecosystems: (1) founders, (2) funding, attractiveness of resources, (3) access to global markets, (4) talent, (5-6) connectivity – local and global, (7) knowledge, experience and (8) organizations, ecosystem actors, events, (9) economic impact.

Findings and facts about local structures are particularly interesting. The preconditions for the self-organization processes of nonlinear (complex) systems can be identified here:

- relationships and assistance between startup founders (e.g. information sharing, resource sharing, etc.) are more determinants of startup success and ecosystem performance than mere physical proximity.
- it doesn't matter how many startups work side by side or close to each other, it matters whether they help each other or not.
- examining two metrics describing the performance of startups (employment and sales), it can be said that in terms of local structure and embeddedness, startups marked with founders with a low number of contacts employ on average fewer employees than better connected startups. Surprisingly, startups led by founders with many connections are often younger companies: they build local connections early and grow faster.
- the importance of community awareness, assistance and local connections – we call this behavior derived from culture – is what ecosystem leaders and developers should pay the most attention to, rather than trying to condense everyone into a single physical space.

However, we must not forget the disadvantages, the negative consequences and the risks. Responsible development requires that we should consider the following issues:

- areas and activities away from ecosystems or hubs do not benefit from desirable and justified subsidies and other opportunities because the ecosystem's capacity to attract resources is relevantly higher and their returns on resources and the multiplier effects are also higher,
- migration of quality workforce and brain drain from less developed areas,
- persistent or growing wealth and income disparities between the innovation and knowledge-based sector and traditional sectors,
- social mobility between social classes and professions is becoming increasingly difficult, as talent management, skills development, enabling environments and equal opportunities are more likely to take place in areas covered by ecosystems, where other agglomeration benefits can also be expected,
- the crowding-out and market-distorting effects of state-funded development,

- technological development may be accelerated by direct overheating or by organic evolutionary trajectories of innovation to a degree that the supply side of the labor market cannot follow in time and may lead to an unprecedented devaluation of people's traditional working skills,
- the accelerating shift towards technological singularity is increasingly obscuring the vision of balanced development.

Knowing the disadvantages and risks, now we can ask the question: is the development of technology startup ecosystems an option or the only viable path? In our current position, the latter is the correct answer. Of course, using the naive and optimistic assumption that negative effects can be reduced either through government intervention or through self-control resulting from recognition, or by responses and selection processes generated by a highly developed culture. If we accept the answer, we will also have to calculate the opportunity costs of the passivity. The lack of innovation performance compared to other countries, ecosystems, hubs, the lack of foundation, realization and development of startup ecosystems interpreted in this context, will only exacerbate the disadvantages and risks outlined above, leaving heavy debt to future generations.

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

**FOCUS OF
OUR STUDY**

3. FOCUS OF OUR STUDY

Innovation startup ecosystems are extremely complex structures, therefore startup ecosystems can be analyzed from a wide variety of perspectives. From our own perspective, we were interested in how the most relevant development factors appear, evolve and interpreted in the countries selected. In this regard, we also present interesting and relevant facts as well. One of our key objectives was to point out that there are a great number of talents in the EASA region who have huge potential for innovation.

For the preparation of this White Paper, we processed secondary sources (a total of 80 references) and conducted our own research. We used the subsequent methods: questionnaires, mathematical statistical analyzes for evaluation and interviews with startup incubators/accelerators and investors.

The following section provides a general overview about the startup ecosystems operating in the EASA countries.

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

**COUNTRY
BY-COUNTRY
ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

ARMENIA

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.1 ARMENIA (ARM)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

The Armenian startup ecosystem has all the preconditions for a startup to be born and grow. Armenia is the cradle of aspiring local startups. During the past few years, many organizations and foundations created an atmosphere to support local startups by organizing events, programs, mentorships, funding etc. Despite the strong will the Armenian innovation ecosystem is characterised by a relative lack of intermediary organizations, a range of public-private partnerships and high degree of independence from the government (lack of for-profit initiatives by the private sector).

In recent years, the Armenian innovation ecosystem has been changing rapidly with the appearance and disappearance of new actors, including governmental and private organizations.

Most relevant actors which have remarkable effects on the ecosystem: Science and Technology Council; Industrial Council; Information Technology Development Support Council; Business Support Council; SME Development Council.

These consultative and coordinating bodies involve representatives from state bodies along with stakeholders from business, academia and civic society.

Enterprise Incubator Foundation (EIF) recently covers general support to innovation in high-tech sectors. Thanks to the Enterprise Incubator Foundation, Armenia has a number of public private partnership initiatives which provide co-working spaces, training, funding and networking. As a consequence world-famous tech companies have opened their representative offices in the country, including Synopsis, IBM, Cisco, Microsoft, Oracle, VMWare, and many more.

The Technology Transfer Association was established in 2001 and is targeted at providing assistance in spheres of technology transfer for companies affected by innovation and high-tech.

The National Centre of Innovation and Entrepreneurship – established in 2009 – is aiming to provide innovation assistance services.

The main state bodies responsible for research and innovation activities in Armenia are the Ministry of Economic Development and Investments (MEDI) and the State Committee of Science (SCS).

Information Technologies (IT) is the leading sector in Armenia involved in strong innovation activities and enjoys priority as stated by the government. It is driven by young dynamic Armenian enterprises, startups with solid connections with international companies.

Numerous successful startups have emerged in the IT industry that have received global financing and have managed to penetrate the global IT market such as Picsart which collected USD 35m capital (including from Sequoia). Large-scale acquisitions in the industry include Monitis (acquired by GFI Software in 2011), VMWare (acquired Integrien, ca. USD 100m) and Oracle (acquired LiveLook aimed at becoming a regional R&D hub).

Substantial progress has also been made in creating an enabling, innovation-supporting environment which is focusing on its tangible infrastructure: free economic zone, technoparks, innovation centres, educational labs and other enabling platforms. The structure of the innovation (startup) ecosystem is depicted by the following figure (see Figure 1.):

FIGURE 1. The structure of the Armenian technology ecosystem.
 Source: European Commission–Kantor Management Consultants (2018)

In the interest of the development of local startups, the following incubators and accelerators operate in Armenia:

AUA EPIC – American University of Armenia Entrepreneurship and Product Innovation Center is a platform for promoting entrepreneurial education, cross-disciplinary collaboration, and start-up venture incubation. EPIC aims to develop knowledgeable, efficient, and experienced entrepreneurs to address the needs of Armenia and the world beyond. EPIC provides an ecosystem for AUA's emerging entrepreneurs, consisting of first-class facilities and collaborative workspaces, programs and events, and a network of mentors, advisors, and investors.

<https://epic.aua.am/aboutepic/>

Beeline startup incubator is a platform, where startups with a great potential of success will be educated by industry leaders and communicate with successful entrepreneurs.

<https://incubator.beeline.am/>

FAST Foundation is building an ecosystem of innovation to lead scientists, technologists, and innovators in Armenia and beyond to success on the global stage. With a focus on entrepreneurial endeavors, FAST empowers innovators to bring cutting-edge, commercially viable, and globally competitive solutions to life.

<https://fast.foundation/en/home>

ISTC Foundation is one of the leading innovation centers in Armenia, founded by joint initiative of IBM, USAID, Armenian Government and Enterprise Incubator Foundation since 2015. Leveraging resources provided by IBM, USAID, EIF and other partners, ISTC has created a unique platform gathering students, professors, researchers, and startup enthusiasts for building innovative solutions to the global challenges. ISTC is devoted to contributing to position Armenia as one of the leading tech hubs of the world.

<https://www.istc.am/>

Start Doon as the French-Armenian business accelerator, StartDoon represents an international bridge of communication and collaboration offering startups and SMEs business development and acceleration services in both local and international markets.

<https://startdoon.com/>

Yerevan Startup Grind is a branch of the international community of startups, founders, innovators, and creators. Startup Grind educates, supports and connects startups and entrepreneurs with various conferences and events.

<https://www.startupgrind.com/yerevan/>

In order to respond to challenges and to alleviate the shortages listed above, Armenia formulated different strategies. The most important documents are the following:

- Innovation Strategy 2011-2020,
- Strategy on Development of Science 2011-2020,
- SME Development Strategy 2016-2018,
- Science and Technology Development Priorities 2015-2019,
- Digital Transformation Agenda,
- Innovation Development Strategy and Roadmap,
- ICT Development Strategy.

The most important innovation policy challenges are in this context:

- weak linkages between researchers and business,
- lack of business support organisations,
- lack of early stage financing including venture investors,
- fragmentation of the innovation ecosystem (the reason for the fragmentation is the absence of common framework for innovation),
- the country does not have a common set of research funding mechanisms and a stable innovation ecosystem,
- another important issue that differentiates Armenia from similar countries is lack of its own financing of projects and policies,
- Armenia lacks well-developed ICT clusters,
- underutilisation of public procurement for innovation.

Despite all the difficulties some promising and prosperous startups can be mentioned operating in Armenia or achieved global success:

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

Embry Tech (est. 2017) Embry Sensorized Insoles help people sit less, move more and manage weight. Embry Tech represents smart insoles that you put inside your shoes and link to your phone. It measures your body weight fluctuations without a scale using patent-pending technology.

[<https://embry.tech/>](https://embry.tech/) [<https://www.linkedin.com/company/embrytech/about/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/embrytech/about/)

Joomag was founded in 2009. Joomag is the all-in-one platform offering a suite of integrated solutions for every content marketing, digital publishing, corporate communications and sales engagement needs. Joomag is working with 500,000+ clients worldwide including companies like KPMG, Cosmopolitan, IBM, Stanford, Harvard.

[<https://www.joomag.com/en/>](https://www.joomag.com/en/)

Krisp (est. 2017) is an AI-powered noise cancelling app that removes background noise and echo during online calls in real time. It works across any communication, conferencing, streaming and recording app and can be used with any wired or wireless microphone, speaker and headphones.

[<https://krisp.ai/about-us/>](https://krisp.ai/about-us/) [<https://www.linkedin.com/company/krisphq/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/krisphq/)

Picsart was founded in 2011 by Hovhannes Avoyan. Picsart is a full ecosystem of free-to-use content, powerful tools, and inspiration from other creators. It's a virtuous circle of inspiration and creation. And the circle is growing. With a billion downloads and more than 150 million monthly active creators, Picsart is the world's largest creative platform. Picsart – a photo editing and drawing tool – has had a rapid growth since the day it was launched and is for all those people who value art, colorful visuals and exchange of inspiration. It has a diversity of tools which create an enjoyable experience.

[<https://picsart.com/about-us>](https://picsart.com/about-us)
[<https://www.linkedin.com/company/picsart-photo-studio/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/picsart-photo-studio/)

Service Titan was founded in 2012 by Ara Mahdessian and Vahe Kuzoyan. ServiceTitan is the world's leading and fastest-growing software technology platform for the trades, a trillion-dollar global industry. The company helps small business entrepreneurs run and grow their businesses. Today, ServiceTitan powers the businesses of more than

5,000 customers, is backed by the world's leading venture capitalists, and continues to target incredible growth.

<<https://www.servicetitan.com/company>>
<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/servicetitan/>>

SuperAnnotate AI is an end-to-end platform to annotate, train and automate your computer vision pipeline. The company's mission is to provide the fastest end-to-end platform for computer vision engineers and labeling teams to annotate, manage, and automate computer vision projects.

<<https://www.superannotate.com/company>>

Renderforest is an all-in-one branding platform offering users the best online tools to create high-quality videos, graphic designs, logos, mockups, and websites with minimal time and effort, it was founded in 2013.

<<https://www.renderforest.com/about>>
<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/renderforest/about/>>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

Catalyst Foundation (2019): Tech and Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Mapping.

<<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Tech-and-Entrepreneurial-Ecosystem-Mapping-web.pdf>>

Davtyan, M. (2021): Startup Ecosystem Or Armenia As The World's Next Technological Hub. I-AM.AM First Global Armenian Directory.

<<https://i-am.am/startup-ecosystem-or-armenia-as-the-worlds-next-technological-hub/>>

Yushkevich, N. (2019): The startup ecosystem of Armenia. Startup Jedi.

<<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-armenia>>

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

AZERBAIJAN

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.2 AZERBAIJAN (AZE)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

Azerbaijan is a country rich in natural resources and consequently the largest economy in the Southern Caucasus. The main focus is on traditional industrial economy and hard infrastructure, innovation and startup ecosystem has not received the necessary attention and development. According to World Bank, expenditure on R&D in Azerbaijan remains lower than in EU and not outstanding compared to other CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, in 2018 it accounted only for 0.18% of GDP (World Bank, 2021).

Several factors can be identified that inhibit growth of innovation and the development of the startup ecosystem:

- limited access to finance, lack of risk/venture capital, neither local nor foreign private companies are keen to invest into R&D activities. Therefore, most of the investments are coming from the state,
- limited competition, small market,
- weak entrepreneurship culture, low quality of business management,
- quality of governance and bureaucracy,
- limited number of professional stakeholders who support innovation, research and infrastructure and provide financial instruments for research, most of the ecosystem members provide advice and consulting as well as help grants access to networks and help in establishing collaboration among different stakeholders,
- lack of relevant tax incentives focusing on startups, Azerbaijan has introduced tax incentives to encourage R&D activities and development of tech parks, however, these incentives are mostly helping big enterprises instead of creating incentives for startup support,
- weak innovation linkages.

Despite these limitations, the current trend of development of ICT and innovations ecosystem is promising in Azerbaijan due to the governmental efforts and commitments. The Azerbaijani government has been taking a series of measures to support startups in the country including the establishment of the State Fund for Development of Information Technologies which is providing investments, the establishment of a joint consortium with the participation of the Innovation Agency under the Ministry of Transport, Communications and High Technologies, AzInTelecom LLC and companies including Lenovo, Nutanix, and iQRex. Currently the main drivers of growth are government policies on liberalisation of the sector, and digitalisation of the society.

To conclude, Azerbaijan has a relatively limited number of private sector stakeholders helping innovative startups and SMEs. The structure of the innovation ecosystem is presented by the following figure (Figure 2.)

FIGURE 2. The structure of the Armenian technology ecosystem.
Source: European Commission–Kantor Management Consultants (2018)

In order to develop local startups, the following incubators and accelerators operate in Armenia:

Azerbaijan 500 ASAN Startup Program is a virtual program designed to support aspiring entrepreneurs in Azerbaijan over 21 weeks of world-class programming and mentorship. This program is designed specifically for innovative Azerbaijani entrepreneurs looking to find fellow co-founders and launch a startup with confidence. The program will be offered at no cost to founders and will be entirely virtual.

<https://ecosystems.500.co/azerbaijan500asan>

GIST IHub: Azerbaijan – SUP Accelerator. SUP is an intensive accelerator program that helps startups grow in Azerbaijan and expand to international markets. SUP intends to be a melting pot for local startups by providing access to capital, mentorship, customer acquisition, and product development. SUP VC is an intensive accelerator program that helps startups grow and expand to international markets. During the 3 month program startups build their products, learn different practices that are applied in an international environment and the program is finalized by Demo Day. SUP VC intends to be a melting pot for our startups by providing access to capital, mentorship, customer acquisition and product development. With dozens of mentorship networks across the globe, SUP VC delivers the knowledge, international practice and the best entrepreneurial journey.

<<https://www.gistnetwork.org/gist-ihub-azerbaijan-sup-accelerator>>

<<https://sup.vc/#about>>

Innovation Agency Azerbaijan. The Innovation Agency was established under the Ministry of Transport, Communications and High Technologies of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the basis of the State Fund for Development of Information Technologies and “High Tech Park” LLC, which are subordinated to the Ministry of Transport, Communications and High Technologies of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Innovation Agency sustains local business entities in acquiring modern technologies and technological solutions, organizes their transfer, supports innovation-oriented scientific research and encourages innovative projects, including startups by funding them through grants, concessional loans and venture capital fund.

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovation-agency-azerbaijan/?original-Subdomain=az>>

INNOLAND Azerbaijan is an incubation, acceleration and research center created to develop the private sector, promote innovation and expand the startup movement both in Azerbaijan and beyond its borders. INNOLAND consists of an incubator, an accelerator, a co-working space and an IT Training and Education Center. The IT Training and Education Center is a place where young people will be taught programming, information technologies and coding skills.

<<http://innoland.az/en>>

NEXT STEP is a Startup Ecosystem player supporting all of Azerbaijan and anyone who wants to connect to the Azeri community. The organization teaches best practices to early stage entrepreneurs that have a global vision and are looking to engage and grow together with partners and customers worldwide. Education and Mentorship is at the foundation of its philosophy. NEXT STEP supports companies at both the Incubation and Acceleration steps.

<<http://icnextstep.com/about-us/>>

Startup Azerbaijan. The main goal of the Startup Azerbaijan project is to improve the investment climate of the country's ICT sector, identify the best internet and IT projects, and assist in turning innovative ideas into successful business areas.

Azerbaijan places a strong focus on national strategies for research, innovation, ICT and startups. The most important documents are listed below:

- Azerbaijan 2020: Vision of the Future,
- Azerbaijan Strategic Roadmap for National Economy,
- National Strategy on Development of Information Society in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2014-2020,
- Strategic Roadmap for Development of the Telecommunication and ICT.

Despite all the difficulties some promising and prosperous startups can be mentioned operating in Azerbaijan or achieved global success:

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

AZEREX is an Idea Developers Fast-Paced startup SMB company. The goal is to build web projects that offer beautiful experiences. AZEREX is also a NATO (The North Atlantic Treaty Organization) registered commercial entity for doing business with international governments. We've experience in developing complex software solutions for enterprises, SMBs, startups and can help your business discover new opportunities for growth and develop comprehensive product strategies.

<https://www.azerex.net/about-us-2/>

Buglance speeds up the testing process in a unique way that companies get their initial bug or issue reports in the shortest time as possible. The company helps businesses to deliver software their users want with crowdsourced testing solutions.

<https://buglance.com/about>

CRBN Tech is a full-service software development company of engineers, designers, and developers founded in 2017. Developers at CRBN Tech make it possible to turn clients' business ideas into successful software solutions that meet their business requirements and contribute to their strategies.

<https://crbn.az/> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/crbn-az/about/>

Fonibo includes a pharmacy, market, restaurant and many other shopping facilities, special express delivery, selection from thousands of products, fast orders, etc. Many advantages such as to make it easier for people to use and to have a successful experience in online shopping. The main goal is to make people's lives easier by making the best use of the opportunities that technology creates for us.

<https://fonibo.com/en/mission>

Keepface is a Global Influencer Marketing Platform offering a variety of influencer management tools that allow brands and agencies to work with the most relevant influencers to create engaging, native and selling content. The automated platform allows companies to collaborate with influencers at a mass-scale, but in a customized fashion.

<https://keepface.com/site/en/influencer-marketing/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/keepface-influencer-marketing-platform/>

Onneks Lab provides a wide range of services for the design and development of websites and mobile applications.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/onnekslab/about/>

Owbike is a scalable cloud-based website building system. You no longer need to go to studios to create a site. You can create a professional website for your business. Owbike, which has repeatedly surpassed all offers in the country, radically simplifies the work of small and medium-sized businesses' websites.

<https://owbike.com/haqqimizda>

QReact (est. 2016) is an easy-to-use survey software for customers, employees and research. QReact is a modern way to get real feedback from your customers.

<https://www.qreact.net/>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

European Commission, Kantor Management Consultants (2018): ICT Innovation and Start-up Ecosystems – Study Report. HiQSTEP Project.

<<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/3.ICT-innovation-and-start-up-ecosystems.pdf>>

Fitz, M. (2021): 9 Top Azerbaijan Apps Companies and Startups of 2021. BestStartup. Asia

<<https://beststartup.asia/9-top-azerbaijan-apps-companies-and-startups-of-2021/>>

Walkers, P. J. (2021): Azerbaijan launches accelerator for startups targeting European markets. CoFounder – [cofmag.com](https://www.cofmag.com).

<<https://www.cofmag.com/2021/09/azerbaijan-launches-accelerator-for-startups-targeting-european-markets/>>

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

BELARUS

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.3 BELARUS (BLR)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

In a historical context, Belarus was one of the most technologically advanced republics of the former Soviet Union. Most of the computers and computers' components were being produced here. Thanks to the interdisciplinary education system in Belarus, local ICT specialists have deep knowledge in mathematics, engineering, physics and other sciences and can be very creative at solving complex problems.

The ICT sector plays a key role in the Belarusian economy. Due to the accumulated knowledge and flexibility the sector seems to be crisis resistant and has great potential to produce relatively high value added. As of 2016, the gross value added of the Belarusian ICT sector amounted to 1.9 billion EUR or 4.5% of Belarus's GDP.

In many ways, 2020 was a turning point for the global startup ecosystem, and of course for the Belarusian as well. The country and the startup ecosystem are entering a new decade with lots of possibilities and unfortunately with lots of challenges. We try to summarize the most important problems as follows:

- damage to the country's international image,
- declining investor interest,
- changes in the development of the domestic legislative framework, weak legislation in the sphere of entrepreneurship, which leads to low level of innovations in the ecosystem,
- lack of transparency in the system of public procurement,
- ongoing crisis,
- Belarus has low expenditures on R&D (0.6% of the GDP, 2018),
- lack of private supporting institutions such as incubators, business angel networks or venture funds, in Belarus, public funds are the main source of investments in R&D,

- underdeveloped mechanisms of perception of innovations (lack of intermediary organisations the Belarus's innovation system including Technology Transfer Offices, University Incubators and Collaborative Research Centres). There are several barriers to collaboration of academic (universities, Research institutes) and industry (mainly high tech enterprises),
- constrained access to research and infrastructure,
- relatively low share of non-state financing of R&D,
- founders fleeing abroad,
- weak academia-academia collaboration and knowledge transfer,
- huge interest in Belarusian technological talents from neighboring countries

In light of the above, the innovation ecosystem shows the structure below (see Figure 3.):

FIGURE 3. The structure of the Armenian technology ecosystem.
 Source: European Commission–Kantor Management Consultants (2018)

The economic and other crises have severely tarnished the growth potential of the ecosystem. Nevertheless, the ecosystem is showing signs of revival. In terms of the general progress or evolution, the following table (Table 1.) tries to cover the most relevant factors and indicators.

INDICATOR	DYNAMICS	2020	2018 ²
Number of companies that took part in the survey	+21.5%	260	214
Startups older than three years	+134%	26.0%	11.1%
Startups in the growth and development stage	+114%	25.0%	11.7%
Startups that are formally incorporated	+47%	81.7%	55.3%
Startups that work solely on the Belarusian market	-47%	29.8%	56.3%
Startups that have regular income	+67%	46.2%	27.6%
Startups with international teams	+49%	31.7%	21.3%
Startups with founders working full-time	+55%	63.2%	40.7%
Volume of investments, \$M	two times	170	85

TABLE 1. Dynamics of the startup development in Belarus.
Source: USAID–Belbiz Group (2021: 11)

Examining the situation in more detail, the following events and facts can be highlighted.

Belarusian startups closed a number of successful investment rounds. In total they raised about USD 60m in 32 deals. PandaDoc and Flo, two startups with Belarusian founders, had two biggest deals in 2020. They were followed by the classic seed series in Loona and Vochi. GiveAway has been selected for the international accelerator Y Combinator (USA) and other startups have been trained in accelerators globally,

including Starta Ventures (USA), Rockstart (Holland), EXPARA (Singapore), Pulsar (Russia), Upward (USA), MTS Accelerator (Russia).

In order to develop local startups, the following notable incubators and accelerators operate in Belarus:

Rocket DAO is a venture community with hundreds of registered members. Rocket DAO is a marketplace for innovative startups, smartest experts and the most sophisticated investors that provides each party with tools necessary for cooperation and success. The community includes Startup Jedi (media partner for startups), Founders Club – startup studio, Investclub.vc – business angels network and Startup Training Camp acceleration program.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/rocket-dao/about/> <<https://rocketdao.io/>>

The **Startup Hub Imaguru** invests in cutting-edge technology companies from Europe, who create an impact on societal problems, connecting them to top notch tech talent. The mission is to leverage technology as a catalyst of positive change, to further point the tech ecosystem in the direction of societal and environmental challenges. It offers co-working space to innovative entrepreneurs, holds educational events and meetups, provides access to a large community of venture market representatives of the country, organizes large field-specified conferences (GEW Belarus, Venture Day Minsk).

<https://imaguru.co/>>

TechMinsk Accelerator was founded in 2013 with the support of USAID and based at Imaguru Startup HUB, TechMinsk is designed to help top innovative startups from the region scale globally. The accelerator helped the following companies to grow: MSQRD, Trackduck, PandaDoc, StoryLine, FriendlyData, OneSoil etc.

<https://techminsk.com/>>

In Belarus the innovation related strategies are mainly focusing on wider social and economic issues:

- The Strategy on the Development of Informatisation in the Republic of Belarus for 2016-2022.
- The National Strategy for Sustainable Social and Economic Development of the Republic of Belarus for the period through 2030.

Leaving many problems behind some promising and prosperous startups can be mentioned operating in Belarus or achieved global success:

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

Apalon is a successful mobile development company. It is part of a leading media and internet company IAC. The total amount of the apps' downloads exceeds 600 millions. Apalon's portfolio includes the best-selling and award-winning applications, such as NOAA Weather Radar Live: Clime, Weather Live, Productive, Pixomatic, Sleepzy, and more.

<<https://apalon.com/>> <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/apalon/>>

Belka Games is a game developer and publisher operating since 2010, one of the fastest growing companies in the industry with offices in several cities and countries. Belka Games handles all sides of the game development and marketing process: from creating and testing prototypes to LiveOps and analytics. Clockmaker, Funky Bay and Solitaire Cruise are 3 top grossing projects of the company with >1 million users playing daily.

<<https://belka-games.com/about/>>
<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/belka-technologies/about/>>

Beesender is the leading add-on for chats and chatbots on the Creatio marketplace. Beesender helps you to develop relationships with your customers even if you work from home. We will robotize some of your most critical business processes for customer care, sales, marketing and HR.

<<https://beesender.com/>>

Easybrain was founded in 2016, Easybrain is a mobile game developer with more than 1 billion downloads. In 2021 Easybrain merged with Embracer. As part of the Embracer Group, Easybrain continues to develop strong mobile game titles and strive towards new achievements.

<<https://easybrain.com/>>

Fabby is an app that automatically edits photos and videos like a professional designer.

<<http://www.fab.by/>>

GanttPRO GanttPRO is an online Gantt chart software for project management with 700k+ users all over the world. They have created an online Gantt-chart software that lets everyone build comprehensive project plans in a few minutes, effectively collaborate on projects with team members, set accurate estimates and track the progress of projects.

<<https://ganttpro.com/about-us/>> <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ganttpro/>>

Onde stands for on-demand services. Onde product is a dispatch platform with apps for the ride-hailing companies around the Globe. It is based on cutting-edge mobile taxi apps as well as web dispatch panel. The whole solution is hosted on the cloud helping our clients to save on infrastructure costs.

[<https://onde.app/>](https://onde.app/) [<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ondeapp/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/ondeapp/)

OneSoil: The precision farming platform that uses satellite imagery and machine learning to help monitor sown areas, predict and plan the farm operations, increase productivity, and save resources.

[<https://onesoil.ai/en/>](https://onesoil.ai/en/) [<https://www.linkedin.com/company/onesoil/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/onesoil/)

PandaDoc empowers teams to easily communicate with customers through personalized documents that can be created in minutes, build meaningful relationships, and save more time.

[<https://www.pandadoc.com/about/>](https://www.pandadoc.com/about/)

RocketData RocketData is an easy-to-use platform to manage your company's business information and reviews among 30+ location-based services: maps, search engines, all popular directories, GPS devices and social networks. RocketData adds information about your company to these services, finds mistakes, fixes them and protects your data automatically. RocketData also helps your business to engage with local customers wherever they are talking through. The platform monitors and gathers customer feedback and provides the tool to answer it from a single interface.

[<https://rocketdata.io/>](https://rocketdata.io/) [<https://www.linkedin.com/company/rocketdata-io/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rocketdata-io/)

Scorum is the first blockchain powered sports media platform. Scorum is a growing IT product company founded in 2017. We develop AI-powered high-load B2B products for online entertainment.

[<https://www.linkedin.com/company/scorum/about/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/scorum/about/)

Synesis Group is a technology firm headquartered in Minsk, Belarus. Founded in 2007 as a software design house, Synesis helped Viber, Yandex, Alfresco, and other well-known companies to develop successful products. Today, more than a billion people worldwide are using these products daily. As of today, Synesis has evolved into a smart city provider with a comprehensive product portfolio for Public Safety, Secure Messaging, Cybersecurity, Event Management, and Instant Lotteries. With a team of 400+ world-class engineers, Synesis is well-positioned to deliver production-level software in Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, and Cloud Computing.

[<https://synesis-group.com/about/>](https://synesis-group.com/about/)

Verv (est. 2013) helps people achieve personal goals, embrace a healthy lifestyle and happier life through simple and effective mobile solutions.

[<https://verv.com/about/>](https://verv.com/about/)

Viber is a calling and messaging app that connects people—no matter who they are, or where they're from. Each month, hundreds of millions of people connect, for free, with their loved ones via messaging, high-quality voice and video calls, and more.

[<https://www.viber.com/en/about/>](https://www.viber.com/en/about/)

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

European Commission, Kantor Management Consultants (2018): ICT Innovation and Start-up Ecosystems – Study Report. HiQSTEP Project.

[<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/3.ICT-innovation-and-start-up-ecosystems.pdf>](https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/3.ICT-innovation-and-start-up-ecosystems.pdf)

CIVITTA (2021): Belarus Startup Report – Report for 2020. CIVITTA – The Challenger Advisory

[<https://civitta.com/articles/civitta-together-with-bulba-ventures-released-the-third-overview-of-the-startup-ecosystem-of-belarus>](https://civitta.com/articles/civitta-together-with-bulba-ventures-released-the-third-overview-of-the-startup-ecosystem-of-belarus)

Seedtable (2021): 98 Belarus Startups to Watch in 2021.

[<https://www.seedtable.com/startups-belarus>](https://www.seedtable.com/startups-belarus)

USAID, Belbiz Group (2021): Bad Year – Belarus Startups 2020.

[<https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00XDKJ.pdf>](https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00XDKJ.pdf)

Yushkevich, N. (2020): The startup ecosystem of Belarus. Startup Jedi.

[<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-belarus>](https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-belarus)

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

GEO **ORGIA**

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.4 GEORGIA (GEO)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

The Georgian startup ecosystem has undergone significant and rapid changes in recent years. Current situation can be described with a lot of attention and interest in startups, startup ecosystem development and many stakeholders are committed to formulate a vibrant community.

The Association Agreement with the EU (came into force in 2016) and a preferential trade regime, Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) have given a big push to these changes. As a consequence EU best practices can be used in the Georgian innovation ecosystem. Georgia's ecosystem is transforming in the right way and is starting to resemble ecosystems in the EU.

The establishment of many specialized government bodies, institutions also served the development.

The most significant and well-known of these organizations is GITA. The agency is formally in charge of innovation policy elaboration and implementation. Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency's mission is a formation of an ecosystem which improves all kinds of innovations and technologies in Georgia, to promote a commercialization of knowledge and innovations, to stimulate using them in all fields of economy, to create an environment for the growth of innovations and high-tech products and developing high-speed internet nationwide <<https://gita.gov.ge/eng/static/3>>. The whole structure of the public institutions and other stakeholders fostering innovation can be seen in the following figure (Figure 4.).

FIGURE 4. The map of the Georgian public policy stakeholders affecting innovation. Source: European Commission–Kantor Management Consultants (2018)

Despite of functioning governmental bodies, it still lacks private sector actors involved in the startup ecosystem.

Even though Georgia’s development processes are transforming in the right way, there are a number of challenges that have to be overcome in order to build up a world-class startup ecosystem.

The most important challenges are listed below:

- small size of the market,
- tools with key importance for commerce (such as PayPal) are not available,
- e-commerce/fulfillment is still in infancy, existing tools are not well known,
- low quality of higher education and scientific research institutions.

- weak links between researchers and businesses,
- lack of qualified labour force, especially coders and IT experts,
- lack of specialized funding for early-phase startups, there are no existing and active angel networks (however, their establishment and development is in progress),
- in the absence of a developed startup ecosystem, there are not many knowledge sharing possibilities, collaborations and startup events, and no immediate access to peers or professional services like graphic design, tax, accounting, legal advice, or targeted e-solutions.

In order to develop local startups, the following remarkable incubators and accelerators operate in Georgia:

FabLab GTU is located at the Georgian Technical University. FAB LAB – The primary goal is to create a union of inventors, innovators, enterprises, enthusiasts and other interested stakeholders which finally reflects on economic growth. priorities of the FabLab GTU are: creation and further development of startups; creation jobs by means of startups; invention/creation of innovative products. The project of the FabLab GTU was financed by Tbilisi City Hall, “Municipal Services Development Agency”.

<<https://www.fablabs.io/labs/gtu>>

GITA Business Incubator. GITA has an in-house Business Incubator program. The agency offers a set of products and services to interested parties and potential beneficiaries, which is focused on helping the innovations and technology oriented entrepreneurs and startups.

Now it encompasses small grants programs, Startup Friendly, Startup Beats, Boot Camp, common working space, Incubator, Registry of Ideas, training portal and the IT support system is a combination of products and services that are key tools for developing a vibrant startup ecosystem.

Impact Hub Tbilisi

Impact Hub Tbilisi is a co-working space where participants can meet, collaborate, produce, learn, network, create. This is the place where change goes to work. Impact Hub Tbilisi is the place for individuals and organisations to create a better world. Connected to 100+ Impact Hubs and 20000+ members all around the world, Impact Hub Tbilisi offers a unique ecosystem of resources, inspiration and collaboration opportunities.

<<https://tbilisi.impacthub.net/>>

Revenue Capital

Revenue Capital is an alternative investment company developing high-tech solutions that improve trading capabilities in traditional financial markets and the crypto industry. It funds and supports fintech, blockchain, AI, ML, and Web 3 companies.

[<https://revenuecapital.io/en/>](https://revenuecapital.io/en/)

Spark – Business Accelerator

Spark is a joint project of Tbilisi City Hall and the European Union, which offers special business development programs to existing small and medium-sized businesses and startups. Spark is a hub for people who have business ideas but do not have access to the resources to turn a business idea into a business plan and are not ready to implement it.

[<https://accelerate.ge/?lang=en>](https://accelerate.ge/?lang=en)

In Georgia the innovation related strategies are mainly focusing on wider social and economic issues, especially in connection with digital transformation:

- Social-Economic Development Strategy of Georgia “GEORGIA 2020”,
- Digital Georgia.

In the light of the many challenges some promising and prosperous startups can be mentioned operating in Georgia or already achieved global success:

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

CNICK „smart rings” develops wearable technologies for enabling the most seamless and reliable authentication. The startup was created by students of the Free University of Tbilisi in 2016. The data in the ring is entered and updated through the application on Android. The project received funding from the “Startup Georgia” program. The smart rings can be used for paying and as a TESLA key: CNICK Rings are compatible with all the Tesla Model 3/Y and 2021 Model S/X.

[<https://teslaring.com/pages/about>](https://teslaring.com/pages/about)

[<https://teslaring.com/pages/tesla-owners-clubs>](https://teslaring.com/pages/tesla-owners-clubs)

Deskomy created a cloud platform for you to back up, save and secure your files with a simple drag & drop. You can access it from anywhere, anytime on any device.

<<https://deskomy.com/en-us/about>>

InvoiceOcean is a simple application that allows you to issue a variety of invoices and related documents online. It operates in the SaaS environment, meaning that all data is stored on the Cloud and is accessible at all times via computer, tablet or smartphone. The software is protected by the SSL encryption code, which is the highest possible security standard, which is also used in online banking.

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/invoiceocean/about/>>
<<https://invoiceocean.ge/>>

LiveCaller provides a cloud based customer communication software designed for companies. Free web call with online chat, omni channel and co-browsing.

<<https://livecaller.io/about>>

Spot The Fire is a service for detecting fires in woods at early stages. With the help of an application, any person with a smartphone and Internet can warn about the oncoming natural disaster.

<<http://spotthefire.surge.sh/>>

Swoop is an e-commerce startup. Established in 2010, Swoop is a top-two local player in the deals & discounts sector in Georgia. It usually features 1000 deals per day on average. Swoop is fully integrated with eMoneyConnect, allowing all eMoney users to use their eMoney credentials to login and their digital wallets to pay.

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/swoop-ge/about/>>

WORLD BUS (est. 2019) offers a vast range of IT services for businesses and technophiles in particular. From cPanel shared hosting to virtual datacenters, virtual private server (VPS), dedicated server, domain registration and storage solutions, all our services benefit from continuous innovation and are regularly enriched with new features.

<<https://worldbus.ge/>>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTOR:

Choladze, D. (2020): Startup Ecosystem Summary – Country Guide Georgia. Startup Universal.

<https://startupuniversal.com/country/georgia/>

Gasanova, M. (2020): Georgian Startups Rankings with the Volume of Attracted Investments. Forbes Georgia.

<https://forbes.ge/georgian-startups-rankings-with-the-volume-of-attracted-investments/>

GITA (2021): Startup Ecosystem. Georgia’s Innovation and Technology Agency.

<https://gita.gov.ge/eng>

Gutbrod, H; Dornbusch, N.; Steden, P. (2019): Startup sector in Tbilisi – A bottom-up perspective on challenges and solutions. GET, German Economic Team Georgia/Berlin Economics, Policy Briefings Series, PB/03/2019.

https://www.german-economic-team.com/georgien/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/PB_03_2019_en.pdf

Startup Ranking (2021b): Top Startups – Tbilisi, Georgia.

<https://www.startupranking.com/top/tbilisi>

Yushkevich, N. (2019): The startup ecosystem of Georgia. Startup Jedi.

<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-georgia>

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

KAZAKHSTAN

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.5 KAZAKHSTAN (KAZ)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

Geographically Kazakhstan is located at the heart of Central Asia, and is predestined to flourish along with the region. Strategically, Kazakhstan links the fast growing markets of China and South Asia with Russia and Europe. Kazakhstan is currently diversifying its heavily oil-dependent economy. A proper way for diversification could be the development of a strong startup ecosystem.

The startup ecosystems in Central Asia are now in the formation phase. So far Kazakhstan does not have startups with a billion capitalization, but a number of projects have already managed to reach success both in local and global markets.

Kazakhstan's startup ecosystem is growing at a fast pace in the last five years. This is true both in terms of the number of new companies as well as an ever-growing possibilities for funding. The Kazakh startup ecosystem is valued over USD 100 million. Startup founders in Kazakhstan are young and hungry for success. The startups are concentrated in two cities/hubs: Nur-Sultan and Almaty.

Now, a very strong limitation is the lack of venture capital supporting growth and development. Ecosystem players are committed to accomplish the desired goals and to remove obstacles.

Below, we listed relevant ecosystem actors who often interact with startups (see Figure 5.).

FIGURE 5. Key actors in the Kazakh innovation ecosystem.
 Source: TUZ Ventures–AIFC (2021)

The development of the startup ecosystem is improving year by year, but there are still challenges to be addressed:

- lack of entrepreneurial spirit and innovative attitudes, especially among the older generations due to the historical background,
- shortage of talents, the country must face brain drain,
- poor hard and smart infrastructure, low penetration of iOS devices, limited logistics and underdeveloped online payment systems,
- a school system that responds slowly to the needs of the technology sector,
- slow government decisions and interventions,
- underdeveloped investment sector.

STARTUP INCUBATORS AND ACCELERATORS IN KAZAKHSTAN

Approximately 15 business incubators and accelerators operate in Kazakhstan.

Astana Hub International Technopark of IT startups (est. 2018). It has its own accelerator, holds training and networking events. The community now has 2187 members and 270 registered companies. During its existence, the residents of the Technopark have attracted about USD 50 million in investments.

<https://astanahub.com/>

Business-incubator MOST is the first private business incubator in Kazakhstan that supports technology entrepreneurs at all stages of business development, and is a creative space where future entrepreneurs can work on their projects, exchange experiences, receive mentorship from experienced businessmen and attract funding for capitalization your business ideas. Services offered for startups: acceleration and incubation programs, corporate acceleration programs, consulting and packaging, Startup Studio, attraction of investments, advisory/mentorship.

<http://most.com.kz/en>

Fostering Productive Innovation Project (FPIP). The Ministry of Digital Development, Innovations and Aerospace Industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan with the World Bank implements the Fostering Productive Innovation Project. The aim of the Project is to stimulate high-quality, nationally relevant research and commercialization

of technologies. Project has 5 components: (1) Development of the Knowledge Base for Innovation, (2) Innovation Consortia, (3) Consolidation of the Technology Commercialization Cycle, (4) Strengthening Coordination of the National Innovation System; Enhancing the Capacity of the Existing Institutional Structures and (5) Support Project Implementation.

<https://www.fpip.kz/index.php/en/about-the-project/project-components>

Joint Stock Company “Engineering and Technology Transfer Center” (QazInnovations). The main goal of the Company is to assist in ensuring the coordination of industrial and innovative development processes and providing measures of state support for industrial and innovative activities. QazInnovations was revitalized in 2020 again and has a very ambitious goal that might be useful for startups and the startup ecosystem in near future. Main activities: 1. Information and analysis services, 2. Technology project management, 3. Management of State Innovation Grants.

<https://qazinn.kz/en/4057-2/#>

NURIS Innovation Cluster of Nazarbayev University. It combines a project and commercialization office, business incubator/accelerator, technology and science parks, I2BF-ABC Seed Fund, Digital Creativity Lab, Fabrication Laboratory, Machine Shop. NURIS in figures (as of 2019): 39 startups passed business acceleration and business incubation programs, 17 events have been held since the beginning of 2018 and 70 applications were processed by the Commercialization Office.

<http://en.nuris.nu.edu.kz/>

Tech Garden. The Autonomous Cluster Fund „Park of Innovative Technologies”, operating under the brand name of Tech Garden, was established by the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The main directions of Innovation Cluster development are as follows: (1) Attraction of international anchor companies (TNK) to establish Technology Development Centers, high-tech production facilities and laboratory facilities in the form of a joint venture (50% co-financing). (2) Creating a critical mass of technological companies under the international acceleration program „Startup Kazakhstan”. (3) Development and implementation of the corporate acceleration program. (4) Implementation of innovative projects at the expense of subsoil users’ obligations. (5) Create a Smart Industry Management Platform (SIMP).

https://en.techgarden.kz/about_fund

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

Clockster is your all-in-one blue-collar management tool. The value the company provides comprises of:

- Payroll,
- Time & Attendance with Face ID,
- Time tracking,
- Task management,
- Employee on-boarding,
- Leave management,
- Flexible shift management,
- Time management statistics,
- Various types of reports,
- Full set of APIs for third-party companies.

<<https://clockster.com/en/>> <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/clockster>>

Constant-lab is a software development company helping businesses become more successful and efficient. Based in Astana, Kazakhstan, Constant-lab LLP is a process driven web services company, offering a wide range of end-to-end services in the IT industry.

<<https://www.facebook.com/Constant.kz/>>

EGStic is an online service, designed to make an effective management decision in crop production.

<<https://egistic.kz/>>

Faceplate is a software developer for industrial applications which improves overall equipment effectiveness (OEE). Faceplate is a platform designed for remote monitoring and diagnostics of industrial equipment, increasing overall production efficiency, reducing energy costs per unit of production.

<<https://faceplate.io/eng/>>

Kaspi.kz (est. 2012) is the largest Payments, Marketplace and Fintech Ecosystem in Kazakhstan.

<<https://ir.kaspi.kz/>>

Singularity Lab is a full-cycle company that develops comprehensive innovative solutions using the latest technologies and advanced user experience.

<<https://singularity.kz/en/>>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

Darkhan, S. (2020): Startup Ecosystem in Kazakhstan.

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/startup-ecosystems-kazakhstan-seitkazin-darkhan/?trk=public_profile_article_view>

Dodd, J. (2021): Kazakhstan's established innovation ecosystem leads to thriving startup scene. STARTUPS Magazine.

<<https://startups magazine.co.uk/article-kazakhstans-established-innovation-ecosystem-leads-thriving-startup-scene>>

Entrepreneur HK (2014): Why is Kazakhstan Lacking a Healthy Startup Ecosystem? Entrepreneur Hong Kong.

<<https://entrepreneurhk.org/why-is-kazakhstan-lacking-a-healthy-startup-ecosystem/>>

StartupBlink (2021a): Global Map – Kazakhstan.

<<https://www.startupblink.com/startups/kazakhstan>>

TUZ Ventures, AIFC (2021): The Startup Ecosystem of Kazakhstan. TUZ Ventures & AIFC Astana International Financial Centre.

<<https://tech.aifc.kz/files/pages/2024/documents/14/kz-report-july-2021-1.pdf>>

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

KYR*G*YZSTAN

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

KYRGYZSTAN (KGZ)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

The Kyrgyz startup ecosystem is still in its earliest stage of development, so access to information is limited. Both the challenges and the structure of the ecosystem are difficult to see clearly. However, many ecosystem actors (private or public) are by now already at the right place and are striving to perform at a high level. Currently the driving forces of the development are mainly provided by the government, so the innovation ecosystem predominantly relies on the supportive contribution of the state and other international organizations. The most significant challenges in the country are finding a suitable, highly skilled workforce and a lack of venture capital.

Government agencies, state funded organizations responsible for the development of startup ecosystems:

High Technology Park of the Kyrgyz Republic (HTP) (est. 2008)

HTP is a special tax zone* that supports: domestic high technology industries, computer science and education, the export oriented economy. HTP also provides acceleration programs for IT startups. The special services cover the following areas: web- and software development, IT & network, sales, marketing, big data, blockchain development and interactive centers. **until 2028 Hi-Tech Park residents are exempt from taxes and insurance premium payments, the income tax rate for employees of resident companies is 5%.*

<http://htp.kg/>

State Intellectual Property and Innovation Service under the ПКР Kyrgyzpatent

Kyrgyzpatent promotes the development of innovation and startup ecosystem of the country, programs and projects aimed at the development of the startup community, startup competencies, creating mechanisms for financing startups, access to markets,

getting access to infrastructure for prototyping, testing, finding highly qualified IT professionals and other projects.

www.patent.kg < www.innovate.kg>

State Innovation Center

The first State Innovation Center was opened in Kyrgyzstan in 2021. The Innovation Center was created at the premises of the State Patent and Technical Library under the State Agency for Intellectual Property and Innovation (Kyrgyzpatent). The Center encompasses the following units:

- Fablab: a production laboratory for prototyping and proofing ideas,
- Youth iLab: children's laboratory,
- coworking area,
- conference room with modern equipments,
- meeting rooms,
- patent and technical fund.

STARTUP INCUBATORS AND ACCELERATORS IN KYRGYZSTAN

State Intellectual Property and Innovation Service with the promotion of the Government of Kyrgyzstan, **Kyrgyzpatent** conducts regular competitions named „Startup Kyrgyzstan“. The selected projects can participate in the acceleration program where they can get funding. Kyrgyzpatent also provides other programs and projects aiming the development of the startup community and startup competencies (see above).

PEAK Business Innovation Centre – which is the result of PEAK Enterprise and Innovation Programme – is the UK Government's new instrument to promote a stronger, diversified and inclusive private sector, leading to prosperity and stability in the Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan by increasing innovation and growth in startups and MSMEs through the establishment of business and innovation centres and improving the business advisory infrastructure. PEAK offers Kyrgyz startups a variety of different programmes and services: incubation and acceleration programmes; business consultations and mentoring on legal, tax, accounting, marketing; co-working spaces.

<https://peak.kg/en/>>

Business Accelerator Accelerate Prosperity is an initiative of the Aga Khan Organization in Central and South Asia (Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Pakistan). Accelerate Prosperity offers technical expertise, creative financing solutions and market connections for small and growing businesses in emerging regions.

Since 2016, Accelerate Prosperity has supported promising young entrepreneurs through business modelling, 1:1 coaching from staff, mentorship and networking with entrepreneurs, investment readiness, seed and growth financing, investors services and trade facilitation.

https://kg.accelerateprosperity.org/en_new

USAID office in Kyrgyzstan implements its programs for startups, including acceleration programs. In 2019, the Business Accelerator program from the USAID Competitive Enterprise project was launched.

<https://www.usaid.gov/kyrgyz-republic>

John Galt Business Incubator is the first Kyrgyz business incubator and accelerator that helps founders build the best companies in the Central Asian region. John Galt is a venture capital arm of the ololo group of companies. Services cover co-working spaces, mentorship and access to its own network of contacts.

<http://ololo.city/> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/johngaltvc/about/>

KG Labs Public Foundation. Mission of KG Labs is to boost the tech ecosystem/ entrepreneurship in Kyrgyzstan. Mentors will help participants improve their ideas and then the projects will be presented to investors. Due to the work of KG Labs a detailed ICT ecosystem database is created and updated. It is also available for the wider public:

<https://kglabs.org/kyrgyz-startup-ecosystem/>

Association of Business Angels of Central Asia

The mission of ABA of Central Asia is to amplify the regional investment market, the regulatory dialogue and to boost entrepreneurship in Central Asia through uniting the investor community and building an educational and collaboration Platform. Association Objectives are listed below:

1. To merge the voice of the Regional Angel Investor Community, to consolidate investment efforts of the angel investors in Central Asia, to represent their interests, to hold events, to advocate for legal considerations, to create and ensure the quality of industry-related best practices as well as to educate and to increase the level of knowledge of the community about the role of angel investors in the economy.
2. To assist entrepreneurs and the startup in finding each other, making possible syndicated angel deals by providing the latest technology solutions in investment management.

3. To create an educational platform for startups and angels of the Central Asian region.

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/association-of-business-angels-of-central-asia/about/>>

<<https://www.abaca.pro/>>

STRATEGIES CATALYZING THE DEVELOPMENT OF STARTUPS AND INNOVATION IN KYRGYZSTAN:

- Concept „Digital Kyrgyzstan“, 2019–2023. Objectives of the concept: to create new opportunities for the population through the development of digital skills; to provide quality digital services; to ensure economic growth through the digital transformation of priority sectors of the economy, strengthening of international partnerships and the creation of new economic clusters.
- “Taza koom” will serve the further development of digital technologies in the economic/social transformation of the country.

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

Fanki is starting its first sales and looking for funding. Fanki’s corporate HR portal increases the efficiency of employee interactions and saves time for managers and HR managers. Fanki’s dashboard helps employees plan their own day and improves communication between them.

<<https://fankihr.com/>>

Mad Devs is specialised for projects requiring the individual technical solutions. The goal is long-term strategic cooperation with clients and providing IT services.

<<https://maddevs.io/about/>>

MUO MakeUseOf was founded in 2007, MUO has grown into one of the largest online technology publications on the web. Our expertise in all things tech has resulted in millions of visitors every month and hundreds of thousands of fans on social media.

<<https://www.makeuseof.com/>>

Groovi Web (Grooviweb.com)

In December 2015, Groovy Web emerged as a fully grown IT services firm under the encouraging leadership of our founders who paved the Way to Excellence and Progress for their team members to follow. Mission of the company: We want to help businesses

ranging from startups to enterprises, who reach out to us with their requirements, in achieving great lengths, expanding their reach, upscaling their products, and generate a large user-base with our outstanding and cost-effective services.

<https://www.groovyweb.co/about-us>

Growave (est. 2014) is the all-in-one marketing platform that helps Shopify brands reach their audience, engage users and increase conversions with ease.

<https://growave.io/> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/growave-io/>

Skalfa The company has been empowering customers with reliable software products since 2004. Their current focus is on business applications for customers on the web and mobile platforms. They build a technical team to tailor to the customers' business process and lead them all the way to superhero status.

<https://skalpa.com/>

SVETOFOR

AI powered leading ecommerce platform (marketplace) in Central Asia, Best online shopping experience in Kyrgyzstan. Dedicated to delight its customers, Svetofor has a 99.5% satisfaction rate and over hundred thousands of happy clients all over Kyrgyz Republic and beyond. Today, Svetofor is a group of companies that provides all services for merchants required to fulfill customer orders and requests.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/svetofor/about/> <<https://svetofor.info/>>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

KG Labs Public Foundation (2021): Kyrgyzstan Startup Ecosystem.

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1xte_QrMvfHGxUAncbRpIL9_JUL17aGrqg_HyjBBOFRE/edit#gid=361801725

Startupcentraleurasia.com (2021): Startup Ecosystem of Kyrgyzstan – Mini-Research.

<https://www.startupcentraleurasia.com/uploads/other/2021-06/%E1%83%A7%E1%83%98%E1%83%A0%E1%83%92%E1%83%98%E1%83%96%E1%83%94%E1%83%97%E1%83%98.pdf>

Startup Ranking (2021a): Top Startups – Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan.

<https://www.startupranking.com/top/bishkek>

Orlova, M. (2021): First State Innovation Center opened in Kyrgyzstan. 24.KG News Agency.

https://24.kg/english/211873_First_State_Innovation_Center_opened_in_Kyrgyzstan/

Peak.kg (2020): Fanki: Startup from Kyrgyzstan in Top-25 of the Entrepreneurship World Cup 2020. [Peak.kg](#) Success Stories.

<https://peak.kg/en/fanki-startup-from-kyrgyzstan-in-top-25-of-the-entrepreneurship-world-cup-2020/>

UNECE (2021): A Roadmap to develop the innovation ecosystem of Kyrgyzstan. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe.

<https://unece.org/economic-cooperation-and-integration/news/roadmap-develop-innovation-ecosystem-kyrgyzstan>

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

MOLDOVA

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.7 MOLDOVA (MDA)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

Moldova is a small, landlocked country in Eastern Europe. Coming with a post-soviet historical background with a highly centralised public system of R&I.

Now, the startup ecosystem relies on external funding and support programs with international mentorship which help boost innovation especially focusing on ICT. Moldova has economic agreements with both the European Union (EU) and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), this fact also could strengthen the „bridge“ role of the country between East and West.

Due to initiatives from the EU, the government and a growing range of supporting organizations, Moldavian startup ecosystem has been gaining speed in recent years. The ecosystem value now is under USD 100m, while the global average is USD 13.68bn. In parallel the total early stage funding was less than USD 50m, for comparison the global average is USD 548m. Moldova is home to 11 business incubators and accelerators. As of 2019 they had together supported more than 100 startups.

The structure of the innovation ecosystem is depicted by the following figure (Figure 6.).

FIGURE 6. The map of the Moldavian innovation ecosystem.
 Source: European Commission–Kantor Management Consultants (2018)

Despite the growing vibration, challenges remain. The following list reveals them.

- the country has serious difficulties in transferring knowledge to markets,
- highly centralised public system of R&I: the R&D activity is highly concentrated around the Academy of Science of Moldova, which formulates the R&D policy, priority actions, and manages most of the budgets allocated to research,
- high level of fragmentation: the policy adoption system is highly dispersed and uncoordinated among institutions,
- low level of innovation applicability: a large part of the research and development carried out has a low added value potential due to the lack of market fit,
- education system focused on teaching: the education system does not produce practical skills and innovative thoughts, as well as little exposure can be observed to international experience. These shortcomings could generate spillover effect in relation with the further careers and innovation potential,
- overreliance on external funding: financing of R&D is mainly focused on the public sector/institutes.

The national government previously adopted a number of strategies and policies in order to become a competitive state and to support digitalisation and innovation. Most relevant strategies are the following:

- Innovation Strategy of the Republic of Moldova for the period 2013–2020 „Innovation for Competitiveness”,
- Strategic Program on Governance Technological Modernisation,
- National Strategy for Information Society Development „Digital Moldova 2020”,
- Strategy to increase the competitiveness of the Information technology industry for the years 2015–2021,
- The Research and Development Strategy of the Republic of Moldova until 2020,
- Roadmap on Enhancing the Competitiveness of the Republic of Moldova,
- In 2019, the Government approved the National Program for the research and innovation sector for the years 2020–2023 and the Action Plan for its implementation,
- Code on Science and Innovation of the Republic of Moldova,
- Moldova 2030 Strategic Priorities Project law is currently undergoing approval in Parliament.

Most relevant startup incubators/accelerators in Moldova to foster innovation and startups:

Business Angels Moldova (BMA) is a group of experienced business people and top managers ready to invest in startups at their early stage of development. BAM is a network of local investors, supported by the secretariat team for executing the daily activities and duties. Business Angels Moldova collaborates closely with both investors and startups, acting as the connecting bridge between them.

<https://www.businessangels.md/>

Digital Park is designed to become a central meeting space for companies active in the IT industry. In this digitization era, where communication and fast connections became vital, Digital Park is the first favorable business development framework in the Republic of Moldova. Digital Park is the answer for connecting technology companies with old history or startup businesses, IT developers, national and international companies, oriented towards innovation and progress, in one same point, in Chisinau.

The fundamental objective of this concept was to create an atmosphere and a “Silicon Valley” infrastructure in Moldova.

<https://digitalpark.md/en/digital-park/design-concept/>

Generator Hub is a project created at the end of the year 2014 in Chisinau, with the purpose of growth in the IT domain in Moldova, by creating an easy to access coworking space, where startups can obtain experience, advice and mentorship, thus creating a community that operates by constantly exchanging experience, ideas and knowledge. In addition, the residents of Generator Hub will also benefit from various development programs like events, seminars, workshops, business training and other.

<https://hub.md/en/about-us-team>

iHUB Chisinau is the most centrally located co-working space in Chisinau. It was created for entrepreneurship and innovation that provides education, access to investors, professional orientation for startups and IT specialists with the most affordable workspace pricing. iHUB is developing an ecosystem of innovative startups in Moldova. iHUB was founded with the support of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Norway through a public-private partnership between the Technical University of Moldova and the ICT Excellence Center – Tekwill, with the purpose of developing the ICT sector and supporting scalable ideas.

<https://www.ihub.md/>

TEKWILL Academy is where people, community, ideas, resources, science, and industry meet to identify, facilitate, and enhance excellence in information technology. Driving the Moldovan ecosystem, as a leading connector and networking facilitator, organizing and supporting local and regional tech-related events (deploy relevant ICT educational content and entrepreneurship activities in the regions Chişinău, Bălţi, Cahul, Comrat). TEKWILL encourages local startups and existing companies to expand and attract international IT companies to invest in Moldova, thus contributing to sector growth.

<https://tekwill.md/about/>

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

Codifun provides innovative learning methods to educate young students.

<https://codifun.com/>

Fentury is dedicated to educating and inspiring a new era of personalized financial management. The goal was to turn personal budgeting from a chore to a pleasant daily habit. Fentury supports over 2,698 banks and is used in 75 countries worldwide.

https://www.fentury.com/support/about_us

Gustos Life is a wine ecosystem platform offering a variety of IT solutions to wine marketers, such as a mobile marketplace, SaaS solution that implements blind tasting by experts, a system for online management of your wine collection, tech solutions for organizing wine tastings etc.

Gustos Life is a worldwide ecosystem for investment in Fine Wine that aims to:

- make this kind of investment with high return rates accessible to a much wider audience,
- solve the issues of Transparency, Traceability, and Trustability of the fine wine investment market. Exclude the possibility of counterfeit and fraud,
- introduce Fine Wine investors to the new emerging markets.

<https://www.gustos.life/> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/gustos-life/>

MEGA Generation was established back in 2013 under the name Moldovan Environmental Governance Academy, or simply MEGA. The original purpose of the organization was to serve as a collaborative platform for us and our stakeholders to experiment with innovative projects and solutions to various environmental and social issues. To fulfill that purpose we at MEGA brought in a series of promising methods, approaches, and technologies, such as games, gamification, e-learning, and social entrepreneurship. Finally, in 2021, MEGA received a professional upgrade and evolved it into a research-training-and-consultancy organization. In line with this the company was rebranded into MEGA Generation.

<http://megageneration.com/about.html>

Retently is a Customer Experience Management Platform for B2B businesses. The company offers a variety of products for a better customer and product experience.

<https://www.retently.com/about-us/>

RitLabs SRL (est. 1998) is a software development company specializing in secure communication products for corporate and private clients. Ritlabs, SRL is based in Chisinau, Moldova.

<https://www.ritlabs.com/en/about/>

Shelfalytics provides high end data analytics to retailers and distributors, collected from the shelves with our modules, sensors, and cameras.

<https://shelfalytics.com/>

Travod is a global provider of expert language services and agile technology solutions for businesses worldwide. Built on a strong belief that content should be accessible to everyone, transcending linguistic, cultural, and geographical boundaries, Travod came a long way to become one of the language industry's leading players.

<https://travod.com/about-us>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

EU4Digital (2021): Guide for building the ICT entrepreneurial ecosystems in the Eastern partner countries: Maturity analysis and recommendations – Final Report.

<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Guide-for-building-the-ICT-entrepreneurial-ecosystems-in-the-Eastern-partner-countries-maturity-analysis-and-recommendations.pdf>

European Commission, Kantor Management Consultants (2018): ICT Innovation and Start-up Ecosystems – Study Report. HiQSTEP Project.

<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/3.ICT-innovation-and-start-up-ecosystems.pdf>

Seedstars Global (2021): These Startups Are Going to Make You Think Twice About Moldova.

<https://www.seedstars.com/content-hub/life/these-startups-are-going-make-you-think-twice-about-moldova/>

Startup Genome (2021): Moldova – startup ecosystem.

<https://startupgenome.com/ecosystems/moldova>

UNIDO (2020): The Innovation Ecosystem of Moldova. Report prepared under UNIDO Country Programme for Moldova 2019–2023. UNIDO – United Nations Industrial Development Organization.

https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/files/2021-02/Report_on_Innovation_Ecosystem_of_Moldova.pdf

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

RUSSIA

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.8 RUSSIA (RUS)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

Russia is the world's 12th largest economy, with a GDP of USD 1.3 trillion, and it is highly dependent on natural resources such as oil and gas. One possible way to reduce dependence on natural resources is to develop innovation. Moreover, the government has developed an even more ambitious plan to transform Russia into a global (leading) innovation hub, with a strong network of world-class tech startups. The Russian innovation startup ecosystem is already diverse, multi-sectoral and has many business models. This diversity is shown by the following figure (Figure 7.).

FIGURE 7. Sectoral breakdown of the innovation ecosystem in Russia.
Source: OC&C (2018)

Regarding the most relevant players, the next figure (Figure 8.) reflects the diversity of the Russian startup ecosystem.

FIGURE 8. Most relevant startup ecosystem players in Russia.

Source: OC&C (2018)

To reach the governmental goals a huge stock of resources needs to be mobilized, including talents, infrastructure and financial resources. In this context, a well balanced (regarding private-public actors) development across all ecosystem dimensions will be essential. This means that the government’s top-down approach – focusing on an extensive physical innovation infrastructure including technoparks and funds – should be completed with other critical elements produced by the activated private sector.

However, the conscious and intelligent development of the ecosystem is limited by a number of circumstances and challenges:

- economic challenges, sanctions, devaluation of the Russian Ruble,
- constrained markets and fewer possibilities to expand and growth due to the above mentioned factors,

- uneven distribution of both startups and the infrastructure, for example 79 percent of all Russian startups are located in Moscow, while this type of concentration is obvious and caused by natural processes in many developing countries in the CIS region, in such a large country more, and more diversified innovation hubs would be necessary,
- low level of R&D expenditures, it currently stands at 1.1% of GDP, 31% of the total funds comes from the government, however increasing private sector participation in R&D would be better,
- Russia's science and innovation culture has not evolved so to value strong business skills, which are necessary features for a strong tech ecosystem,
- policy regulations on digital transformation are often broadly focused,
- much of Russia's private sector is highly concentrated, with a small number of large companies, the oligopolistic market situation does not support intense technological competition and at the same time it reduces the prospects for young tech companies in terms of market entry.

Government investments in a large physical infrastructure and institutions marked by technoparks and incubators, these efforts have contributed significantly to ecosystem development.

FAISE – a foundation formed by the government to promote small innovative enterprises and young innovators. The services provided by the foundation also include startup incubation and acceleration.

<https://fasie.ru/>

Generations. is a corporate accelerator. RVC organized the first tech startup accelerator under the GenerationS brand, which immediately received widespread response from entrepreneurs. The main goal is to help startups efficiently cooperate with corporate partners. We also help corporations find challenging technologies and introduce them into their production chains.

GenerationS is a platform for corporate innovations development; it is the largest corporate accelerator across Russia and CIS. Part of Russian Direct Investment Fund. GenerationS implements comprehensive corporation development programs including in-house programs for intrapreneurship development, acceleration programs for scouting and external project acceleration, and international programs for staff training in innovations development and management methods based on international leading corporations.

The accelerator infrastructure today includes more than 18 000 startups from more than 60 countries and more than 1300 corporate and ecosystem partners. In 2017 GenerationS was recognized as one of the largest Russian accelerators according to the RBC magazine. In 2018 GenerationS became the best corporate accelerator in Europe according to the Corporate Startup Summit. GenerationS is also in the top- 5 best state-owned accelerators in the world according to the UBI Global. Winner of 2020 ITU Innovation Challenge in the category “Ecosystem best practice”. In 2020 GenerationS became a member of the INSME Association, the international network for small and medium-sized businesses under the auspices of the OECD.

[<https://en.generation-startup.ru/>](https://en.generation-startup.ru/)

[<https://www.linkedin.com/company/techstartussia/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/techstartussia/)

IIDF The Internet Initiatives Development Fund (IIDF) is a Russian venture capital fund. The mission is to help Russian-speaking entrepreneurs create tech companies and turn them into global companies that contribute to positive changes and add value to the lives of people around the world.

Their goal in working with entrepreneurs is to ensure the team’s transition to the state necessary for global business scaling and to help it allocate all the necessary resources to fully unleash its potential.

[<https://iidf.vc/>](https://iidf.vc/)

RVC Russian Venture Company (RVC JSC) is a state fund of funds and a development institution in the Russian venture capital market. The mission of the company is to create a mature venture capital market through the consolidation and development of resources, competencies and initiatives on the part of investors, investment portfolio managers and entrepreneurs so as to create and promote innovative products and technologies in priority technology areas, making Russia a leader in the global technology market.

[<https://www.rvc.ru/en/>](https://www.rvc.ru/en/)

Skolkovo Innovation Center Skolkovo Foundation’s overarching goal is to create a sustainable ecosystem of entrepreneurship and innovation, engendering a startup culture and encouraging venture capitalism. The Skolkovo Foundation identified five key areas of potential growth: energy efficiency, strategic computer technologies, biomedicine, nuclear technologies and space technologies. The strategic goal of the Skolkovo Innovation Centre is to concentrate international intellectual capital, thereby stimulating the development of break-through projects and technologies. In the course of implementation of the project, companies that are engaged in innovative

development are discovered. After a selection process, some of these become project participants of the centre.

<https://old.sk.ru/foundation/about/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/skolkovo-foundation/>

According to the data of the Russian Association of accelerators and business incubators (AABIC), in 2018 there were 260 functioning business incubators. Where 151 of them were working in regions and 91 were created on the university bases, 13 incubators were working in clusters and technoparks. Considering accelerators, according to the data of the AABIC, in 2018 there were 103 accelerators. Where 26 of them are private, 22 are corporate and 19 are university-based. Some of them are listed below:

Fintech Lab helps financial market participants find and refine potentially interesting projects in the field of fintech, as well as solve industry-wide tasks, and achieve results faster and cheaper than any participant alone or in a less coordinated interaction could have done. For startups, Fintech Lab offers the opportunity to work with potential customers in the same location and tailor their products to the real needs of financial institutions.

<http://fintech-lab.ru/>

Global Venture Alliance (GVA) is an international company with sites in Silicon Valley and Moscow. GVA brand is a private innovation ecosystem and unites acceleration programs for startups, educational initiatives on professions of the future, investments from our funds and large-scale projects with corporations and the government, aimed at the development of the environment of innovations, which responds to the global challenges.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/gvavc/about/>

Moscow Accelerator is a joint initiative of the Moscow Agency of Innovations and the Moscow Innovation Cluster Fund and is supported by the Moscow Department of Entrepreneurship and Innovation. The initiative is a unique example of collaboration among the city's government institutions, large corporations and startups to fuel the development and growth of innovative business in Moscow.

<https://ma.innoagency.ru/index-en.html>

Sber500 International Accelerator (Joint initiative of Sber & 500 Startups)

This Startup Development Program is Russia's largest ecosystem, Sber and the 500 Startup, one of the world's strongest teams in venture capital and IT business development.

The program for technology entrepreneurs is based on:

- the expertise and experience of 500 Startups - one of the strongest teams in the world of venture capital and IT business,
- Sberbank's support, thanks to which young startups gain access to 60+ ecosystem companies and dozens of Russian and international partners of the Accelerator.

Mission of the accelerator: We are developing startup ecosystems in Russia and internationally. Since 2018, we have been attracting startups from all over the country to help them grow into successful businesses and enter new markets. From the third wave onwards, we will expand our geographical area and work with entrepreneurs from the CIS, Israel and Northern Europe.

[<https://sberbank-500.ru/>](https://sberbank-500.ru/)

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

CINEMOOD is a wireless projector designed as a home theater for children that allows them to interact with technology in dynamic ways, while preserving curatorial power for parents.

Though registered in Russia, its manufacturing is in China, and the company has participated in IIDF's incubator that brings Russian entrepreneurs to Silicon Valley. The company has also launched a campaign on international crowdfunding site Indiegogo that will enable it to raise capital from both foreign and domestic investors.

[<https://cinemood.com/>](https://cinemood.com/)

IVI is one of the biggest Russian startups in the world at the moment. IVI is the No.1. online cinema in Russia, with an audience of over 52 million unique visitors per month. IVI is the leader in the number of content units. In addition, on-air and cable TV channels, sports and music broadcasts, fitness training, children's content and much more are available to IVI subscribers.

[<https://www.linkedin.com/company/iviru/about/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/iviru/about/)

Mail.ru Group is developing a unified, integrated platform for communication and entertainment Internet services. The company owns a leading mail service, one of the most visited portals in Runet, leading Russian-language social networks. The company is actively developing its B2B business, providing companies with tools to simplify workflows and increase their efficiency: among them is the Mail.ru for Business platform, Mail.ru Cloud Solutions and the myTarget advertising platform, which combines the web and mobile audiences of the largest in Russia and the CIS services and social networks.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/mail-ru/>

Playrix is the largest gaming company in the CIS region. It is among the TOP 3 most successful mobile publishers in the world. More than 130 million people play their games every month.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/playrix-entertainment/>

OCSiAI is the only company with a scalable technology for industrial synthesis of graphene nanotubes. OCSiAI is the world's largest producer of graphene nanotubes. In addition to the synthesis of nanotubes themselves, we create industry-friendly technologies for their use in various materials.

<https://ocsial.com/about/>

Ostrovok.ru is Russia's leading online travel booking website for individual travelers. It is about travel, online Hotel booking, international brand, travel industry, and travel technology.

<http://www.ostrovok.ru>

Telegram is a cloud-based instant messaging and voice over IP service. Telegram is the world's fastest and most secure messaging app.

<https://telegram.org/>

Yandex is not only a search engine but also many other convenient services including Yandex.Food, Yandex.Taxi, Yandex.Zen, Yandex.Maps, Yandex.Money, Yandex.Maps, Yandex.Music and other multimedia search, cartographic, market search, reference and information, advertising, statistical, social, personalized web services and mobile applications.

<https://yandex.ru/>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

Fybish, A. (2021): Top Russian Startups To Watch in 2021. Startup Stash.

<<https://startupstash.com/russian-startups/>>

OC&C (2018): Tech Entrepreneurship Ecosystem in the Russian Federation. OC&C Strategy Consultants.

<https://www.occstrategy.com/media/1311/tech-eship-ecosystem-in-focus-countries_russia.pdf>

Yushkevich, N. (2020): The startup ecosystem of Russia. Startup Jedi.

<<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-russia>>

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

TURKEY

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.9 TURKEY (TUR)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

One of the most vibrant startup ecosystems in the region. There are three important development stages in the history of the ecosystem:

- (1) 2000–2009 *The bootstrapping period*: lack of startup investors, most successful startups emerged from the bootstrap model,
- (2) 2010–2017 *Growth period*: supporting actors and investors massively entered the ecosystem, the huge amount of investments resulted in an increase in the number of startups. These new entrants were angel investors, VCs, CVCs and accelerators.
- (3) 2018→ *Take-off period*: the first unicorns and the first IPOs appeared. VCs have raised and begun to deploy their second funds. Parallel with these many scaleups are starting to take their first steps toward global markets. The Turkish Startup Ecosystem is taking off.

To illustrate this dynamic, the following figure (Figure 9.) contains some interesting quick facts.

FIGURE 9. Interesting quick facts in relation with the take-off period of the Turkish startup ecosystem in 2021. Source: Startups Watch–Turkey Investment Office (2021)

Of course, this development phase presupposes the existence of vibrant structures of diverse actors. In every field of the startup ecosystem this advantageous heterogeneity can be observed. The following figures try to catch this diversity and present the most relevant players (Figure 10–12).

FIGURE 10. Most important organizations offering pre-incubation and incubation services in Turkey. Source: Startups Watch–Turkey Investment Office (2021)

FIGURE 11. Selection of startup accelerators in the Turkish innovation ecosystem. Source: Startups Watch–Turkey Investment Office (2021)

BUSINESS ANGEL NETWORKS (Accredited+Non-Accredited)

CROWDFUNDING

TECH ACCELERATOR INVESTORS (Reside in Turkey)

FI/DFI

FIGURE 12. Relevant ecosystem players involved in funding and investment. *Source:* Startups Watch–Turkey Investment Office (2021)

To see the exact numbers, the figures below reflect the evolution of the number of startup incubators and accelerators (Figure 13-14.). Most incubation centers in Turkey have been established by technoparks. While, at the same time, accelerator programs became more specialized and by now they are mainly focusing on the gaming sector.

FIGURE 13. The evolution of the total number of startup incubators in Turkey (2010–2021 H1). *Source:* Startups Watch–Turkey Investment Office (2021)

FIGURE 14. The evolution of the total number of startup accelerators in Turkey (2010-2021 H1). *Source:* Startups Watch–Turkey Investment Office (2021)

The rapidly growing Turkish ecosystem still faces many challenges. Most of them are not compatible with the dynamic, take-off phase:

- relatively low level of funding possibilities,
- the lack of qualified personnel,
- rigid workplace culture,
- extensive bureaucracy, lots of paperwork,
- relatively poor infrastructure and smart infrastructure,
- regarding startup founder migration, Turkey is losing more founders due to HQ relocation than attracting new entrants from other countries,
- the broken investment value chain. In other words, lack of technology investors,
- Turkey still invests significantly less in R&D than its G20 competitors,
- no significant evaluation processes after closing government backed R&D investments and projects. These could induce less efficiency and growth (Kayahan, 2020; Snow, 2017).

Perhaps the strategies that have been developed recently will address these shortcomings as well.

Strategies and visions of the country to continuously support the digital transformation (Daily Sabah, 2021):

- National Artificial Intelligence Strategy for 2021–2025,
- „Digital Turkey”,
- National Technology Move.

The success of the Turkish startup ecosystem is also shown by the growing investor interest in such companies. When we check the breakdown of startup deals by sub-sectors for the Q2 2021 regarding transaction volumes, we find that (1st place) delivery & logistics, (2nd place) gaming and (3rd place) marketplace sectors were highly preferred by investors. The investment amounts were as follows: USD 550m investment to Getir, USD 155m investment to Dream Games and acquisition of GarajSepeti by Kavak Intermediate Holdings for USD 25m.

By number of transactions, Gaming sector was in the first place (15 transactions), FinTech was second with 10 transactions and in third place were HealthTech & SaaS (5-5 transactions)(KPMG, 2021).

If we want to talk about successful Turkish startups, we have an easy task, as there are plenty of them. The Turkish Billion Dollar Club contains such startups which managed to reach 1 billion USD market value.

Peak is a leading mobile technology company with a team who values progress. Peak’s acquisition for USD 1.8 billion in 2020 made it to be the first startup in this club.

<https://peak.com/about>

Dream Games is a mobile gaming company founded in 2019. The objective is to combine technology and creativity to develop high-quality mobile games that will be played for years.

<https://dreamgames.com/>

Getir is a technology company that joins the worlds of mobile technology and logistics, providing unprecedented solutions to the delivery of goods in urban areas.

<https://getir.com/en/about/> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/getir/>

Hepsiburada was founded in 1998 and has been operating under the Hepsiburada brand since 2001, the company became the largest e-commerce platform in Turkey and the surrounding region.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/hepsiburada/about/>

Trendyol was established in 2010 with an ambition to provide customers and sellers a flawless e-commerce experience. By now Trendyol Group is not only Turkey's leading e-commerce company, but also amongst the world's leading platforms.

<https://www.trendyol.com/whoweare>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

Daily Sabah (2021): Turkey rolls out strategic artificial intelligence roadmap.

<https://www.dailysabah.com/business/tech/turkey-rolls-out-strategic-artificial-intelligence-road-map>

Kayahan, D. (2020): Challenges and Opportunities of Developing Startup Ecosystems: Central and Eastern Europe and Turkey Example. Medium.com

<https://medium.com/startup-intellect/challenges-and-opportunities-of-developing-startup-ecosystems-central-and-eastern-europe-and-759f77a0b1aa>

KPMG (2021): Turkish Startup Investments Review – Q2 2021. KPMG Turkey & 212.vc

<https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/tr/pdf/2021/08/turkish-startup-investments-q2-2021.pdf>

Startups Watch, Turkey Investment Office (2021): The State of Turkish Startup Ecosystem. An In-Depth Analysis and Evaluation. Startups Watch & Presidency of the Republic of Turkey Investment Office.

<https://www.invest.gov.tr/en/library/publications/lists/investpublications/the-state-of-turkish-startup-ecosystem.pdf>

Ünsal, S. (2020): Turkish Startup Ecosystem Map [v6.0]. startups.watch (SW)

<https://blog.startups.watch/turkish-startup-ecosystem-map-v6-0-ea9f21362917>

Seedtable (2021): 108 Turkey Startups to Watch in 2021.

<https://www.seedtable.com/startups-turkey>

Snow, A. (2017): Turkey's Technology Startups: U.S.–Turkey Collaboration in a Growing Ecosystem. Turkish Heritage Organization – Technology Brief No.1.

<https://www.turkheritage.org/en/publications/factsheets/issue-briefs/turkeys-technology-startups-us-turkey-collaboration-in-a-growing-ecosystem-4676>

**RIISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

UKRAINE

**ECOSYSTEM
OVERVIEW**

4.10 UKRAINE (UKR)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

In 2020, Ukraine climbed up to 64th position out of 190 countries in the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business ranking. Ukraine is also rated second in terms of speed and depth of business climate improvement. And these favorable conditions can also be observed in relation to the startup ecosystem. Ukraine is 34th among 100 countries in the Global Startup Ecosystem Index in 2021. With over 2,000 startups, the country has a fast-developing startup ecosystem. Kyiv – the largest IT hub in Ukraine – is home to over 1,000 successful startups and other innovative companies. Simultaneously Kharkiv, Odessa, Dnipro, Lviv, and Vinnytsia are also developing as major centres of IT activity and startup clusters, reducing such an unhealthy concentration like in Moscow-centric Russia. Ukraine's startup ecosystem is in the take-off phase. Ukraine's startup ecosystem is in the take-off phase, thanks to its talents, diverse innovation structure and the necessary players who contribute to the development processes. The next figure (Figure 15.) shows us the structural shape of the ecosystem.

FIGURE 15. The structure of the Ukrainian innovation ecosystem.

Source: European Commission–Kantor Management Consultants (2018)

However, the path of development is bordered by serious challenges.

- Ukrainian innovation system requires additional reform of universities and academies inherited from the Soviet economy,
- poor conditions for the researchers have caused significant brain-drain over the last 20 years,
- outdated equipments are relevant problem for the most Ukrainian R&D institutions,
- universities are not involved in R&D activities at a desired level,
- in the economy prevailed traditional sectors (agriculture, metals and heavy manufacturing), which generally have low demand for R&D,
- lack of motivation and ability of financial institutions to support R&D,
- lack of the dialog and cooperation between innovation ecosystem players,
- in spite of the large amount of innovation infrastructure organisations in Ukraine, there is still a deficiency in providing services for startups and innovation companies in general,
- Ukraine has an insufficient level of consulting services,
- despite its innovative technologies and a booming IT industry, Ukraine is not well-known as a technology startup hub,
- shortage on relevant information regarding financial and funding opportunities,
- weak protection of Intellectual property rights,
- there are no tax credits for R&D in Ukraine,
- public support on venture capital funds is weakly developed,
- international cooperation and international knowledge sharing should be improved,
- need to develop critical business skills: many Ukrainian startups pursue innovative ideas or work with world-class technologies, but lack a complete understanding of how to develop a globally-competitive business model,
- legislature concerning ICT (in particular PPP) is still incoherent in Ukraine, which generates disturbances for innovative companies.

Most of the governmental strategies focusing on digital transformation ended in 2020. (See for example: Strategy of innovation development of Ukraine for 2010–2020 in the context of globalisation challenges; Strategy for the development of the information society in Ukraine.) Reliable data on their successful implementation are not yet available. In fact, governmental support for the digital transformation has not stopped here and additional concepts are being developed or their implementations have already started. The following figure (Figure 16.) summarizes the key elements and their contents of the National Digital Agenda.

FIGURE 16. Key elements of the Ukrainian National Digital Agenda.

Source: EY–USAID (2021: 51)

There are various incubators and accelerators in Ukraine to help the benefits of the digital transformation and the development of startups.

1991 Open Data Incubator is Ukraine’s first non-commercial incubator, that helps to transform tons of open data into startups that serve citizens, businesses and governmental institutions.

<http://1991.vc/en/about-incubator/>

Blue Lake Accelerator is a UK based early-stage VC with a unique vision. The accelerator uncovers, invests and supports exceptional founders before they come on to the radar of the mainstream investor community. The focus is on B2B, SaaS Pre-Seed and Seed stage startups although we might be open to other opportunities.

<https://www.bluelakevc.com/>

INDAX production accelerator is a system platform for servicing and scaling small and medium-sized businesses in the industrial sector.

[<https://indax.com.ua/>](https://indax.com.ua/)

IoT Hub Accelerator is an accelerator for IoT startups. IoT Hub community unites result-oriented people with laser focus and passion in one place and time to build tech organizations from idea to cash out.

[<https://iothub.xyz/#about>](https://iothub.xyz/#about)

RadarTech is a technology cluster that unites industrial corporate startup accelerators.

[<https://radartech.com.ua/#about>](https://radartech.com.ua/#about)

Sector X is an innovative platform that combines acceleration and study programs for startups, corporate innovation programs for business, and services for venture investors. Sector X is a B2B/B2C startup accelerator for teams from Ukraine and Eastern Europe in the field of big data, VR/AR, IoT.

[<http://sectorx.city/aboutus/eng>](http://sectorx.city/aboutus/eng)

Scythia Ventures Accelerator is a partnership between early stage venture fund Scythia Ventures and investment platform startup.ua that teamed up together to develop early stage ideas with angel and pre-seed investments of up to USD 100,000 in the ICT focused startups based in the CIS (ex-USSR) region.

[<https://angel.co/company/scythia-ventures-accelerator>](https://angel.co/company/scythia-ventures-accelerator)

YEP is a network of academic business-incubators. They provide a business-related education for youth, contributing to the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of Ukraine.

[<http://www.yepworld.org/en/>](http://www.yepworld.org/en/)

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

It is an interesting fact that many startups that are already known worldwide and all of us use their services all started their journey from Kyiv. A non-exhaustive list follows: Ajax Systems, Grammarly, MacPaw, Netpeak Software, People.ai, PetCube, Preply, Reface and Restream. Other remarkable startups are mentioned below:

Adtelligent Inc. The company is headquartered in New York City, NY, USA with offices in London, U.K, Odessa and Kyiv, Ukraine and expanding geographies around the World. Adtelligent produces all of its technology in-house and has been acknowledged as one of the fastest growing independent technology companies by Inc. 5000 in 2016 and 2017. Adtelligent is a sell side ad technology company providing fully-featured Ad Monetization Platform and Header Bidding Management solutions for publishers. By integrating ad serving for display and video, header bidding wrapper capabilities, and outstream functionality into one holistic stack, Adtelligent has established a new standard for selling inventory to programmatic buyers.

<<https://adtelligent.com/about/>> <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/adtelligent/>>

CEX.IO was one of the first platforms to make fiat-to-crypto transactions accessible by offering card payments and bank transfers to the clients. The company places a great effort into developing and maintaining robust relationships with dozens of reputable banks across the key markets.

<<https://cex.io/about>>

Jooble is the 2nd largest job site in the world. It operates in 71 countries and is visited by 80 million candidates. The company simplifies the job searching process for candidates by displaying thousands of active job ads on Jooble aggregated from different job boards, recruitment companies through XML feeds.

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/jooble/about/>>

Let's Enhance is a deep tech AI company that builds End-to-End imaging solutions for photo enhancement and optimization. This helps to get control over the quality of user-generated content and make it look better for higher conversion rates. The services are used by more than 4m people worldwide and the company's API is automating image enhancement for Fortune 500 companies.

<<https://letsenhance.io/>>

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/letsenhance/about/>>

Letyshops is a company that over 6 years has grown from a startup to the largest cashback service in Ukraine and the CIS region. They have an office in Hungary and R&D centers in Vinnytsia and Kyiv. The service has become popular in Spain, Portugal, Germany, Poland, France, Italy, India and some Latin American countries. LetyShops has more than 8m users.

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/letyshops/about/>>

Mobalytics was founded by a group of passionate gamers, Mobalytics is a rapidly growing esports and gaming startup with a big vision: To help all gamers achieve their full potential while maximizing enjoyment of their favorite games.

<https://careers.mobalytics.gg/?int_source=homepage&int_medium=footer>

Restream allows you to broadcast live video to 30+ social networks at the same time. Millions of people around the world use Restream to reach, engage and monetize their audiences. Their customers include professional and amateur gamers, Fortune 500 companies, media, politicians and celebrities.

<<https://restream.io/about>>

Template Monster is a large digital marketplace with a wide choice of website themes, premium-quality graphics, stunning presentation templates and visuals for online marketing campaigns. The company is in the top 3 of global vendors for web development solutions.

<<https://www.templatemonster.com/about.php>>

<<https://www.linkedin.com/company/templatemonster/about/>>

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

dealroom.co (2020): Consortium of Ukraine's leading ecosystem players team up to launch startup database, led by ICU, powered by Dealroom. [Dealroom.co](#) blog.

<<https://dealroom.co/blog/consortium-ukraines-leading-ecosystem-players-launch-startup-database>>

European Commission, Kantor Management Consultants (2018): ICT Innovation and Start-up Ecosystems – Study Report. HiQSTEP Project.

<<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/3.ICT-innovation-and-start-up-ecosystems.pdf>>

EY, USAID (2021): National Strategy to Increase Foreign Direct Investment in Ukraine. Ernst & Young, United States Agency for International Development.

<<https://ukraineinvest.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/FDI-Strategy-Section-2-Digital-Infrastructure-ENG.pdf>>

StartupBlink (2021b): Global Map – Accelerators in Ukraine.

<https://www.startupblink.com/accelerators/ukraine>

StartupBlink (2021c): Global Map – Ukraine.

<https://www.startupblink.com/startups/ukraine>

Tech Ukraine (2021): 360 Tech Ecosystem Overview – Deep dive into the 360 Tech Ecosystem Overview.

<https://techukraine.org/360-%d1%82%d0%b5%d1%81h-ecosystem-overview/>

UkraineInvest (2021): UkraineInvest Guide – Explore Your Opportunities.

<https://ukraineinvest.gov.ua/guide/>

Ukraine Now (2021): Startup Ecosystem.

<https://ukraine.ua/invest-trade/startup-ecosystem-ukraine/>

USF (2019): Strategic vision 2020–2025. Ukrainian Startup Fund.

https://usf.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/strategy_usf_2020-2025.pdf

4.11 UZBEKISTAN (UZB)

KEY ATTRIBUTES OF THE STARTUP ECOSYSTEM

Uzbekistan, located in Central Asia, is bordered by Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tadjikistan and Afghanistan. Uzbekistan, with a population of ca. 33 million people, is Central Asia's most populous country, thus possessing huge market potential. Similar to other Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan has a very young population, with an average median age of 28.6 years. The country also looks very promising from an economic point of view. The subsequent figure (Figure 17.) provides insight into the quick facts that support our previous statement.

FIGURE 17. Quick facts about the Uzbek economy (2020). *Source: TUZ Ventures–IT Park (2021). Note: the values used here do not reflect the possible impact of the COVID-19 crisis.*

Relying on strong economic fundamentals the government is really committed to create a fertile ground for the birth of a competitive entrepreneurial sector. In 2017, the government established the Ministry of Innovative Development with the goal to ensure accelerated innovation-driven growth in all sectors.

The Uzbek startup ecosystem is in its early premature phase, the first relevant actors have been appearing only in recent years. Brand.uz was the first company which was involved in the startup world in 2001 <<https://brand.uz/about>>. To enhance the emergence of new startups, numerous supporting organizations, mostly owned and managed by the government, have started their work in the last years. The next figure (Figure 18.) reveals the structure of these supporting organizations and the subordinated institutions responsible for implementation.

FIGURE 18. Structure of the governmental organizations and institutions responsible for promoting innovation and the startup community.
 Source: enpact (2019)

The vast majority of Uzbekistani startups (62%) develop their product or service for the Uzbekistan market, whereas only 21% of the founders plan to scale up to CIS countries, however the ability of startups to scale-up very quickly is at hand. 64% of startups began their operations within a year and for most of them, it took less than 6 months to move from the idea/concept stage to fully operational. Most of the startups offer B2B solutions, while operating mainly in the following sectors: e-commerce, EdTech, MedTech, FinTech and AgTech.

To get a deeper and clearer insight, the following figure (Figure 19.) presents the composition of the ecosystem.

FIGURE 19. The composition of the Uzbek startup ecosystem (2020 Q3).
Source: TUZ Ventures–IT Park (2021)

The development of the startup ecosystem is gaining increasing momentum year by year, but there are still challenges to be addressed:

- startup promotion remains relatively centralised due to the strong governmental involvement,
- in the consequence of this strong governmental presence, incentives do not exist for these startups to introduce more target-oriented programs or act in a more efficient way as they hardly face competition and their survival is ensured by the government,
- initiatives from the competitive sector are still rare and mostly driven by highly motivated individuals,
- Uzbek banking sector is opening slowly, more fintech solutions are required,

- Uzbek startup founders must face significant challenges in accessing funds, especially in case of seed investments,
- the number of active business angel investors remains low, there are currently only around 10-15 active business angels in Uzbekistan. But, they are not organised in an angel network,
- there is a lack of knowledge on both sides (investors & startups) about the investment processes and investing in startups in general.

STRATEGIES ADDRESSING INNOVATION AND ECOSYSTEM DEVELOPMENT:

After decades of isolation, Uzbekistan has taken a giant leap to open up its economy by implementing new economic, social and judicial reforms. In 2017, Uzbekistan introduced its first Development Strategy for the period 2017-21. To support the economic development and foster the liberalisation featured among the five priority areas of this program. To serve the digital transformation processes and to support the startup ecosystem the **Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy** was approved in 2020, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The strategy encompasses the following areas: digital infrastructure, e-government, digital economy, national digital technologies market, education and training in the sphere of IT (Khoshimov-Makhmudaliev, 2020).

RELEVANT STARTUP INCUBATORS AND ACCELERATORS:

CAT Science Accelerator for Central Asia is the first accelerator in Uzbekistan for „scientific“ projects and commercialization of scientific developments.

<<https://cat-sa.uz/>>

innoWIUT is the entrepreneurship lab of WIUT. The aim is to accelerate innovation and technological growth in Uzbekistan by bringing together industry leaders to support young-innovators and startup teams.

<<https://inno.wiut.uz/aboutus>>

IT Park Uzbekistan creates a World class state-of-art environment for the development of Innovation and competitive products & services in the field of information technologies, their promotion both in the domestic and global Markets. It provides the innovation culture and entrepreneurial atmosphere for the youth in Uzbekistan. IT Park

specializes in: incubation and acceleration programs, government-supported and private venture funds, IT Academy of International Standard, modern and comfortable co-working spaces and IT areas, legal, accounting and marketing support.

<https://it-park.uz/en/itpark/about> <https://www.linkedin.com/company/itparkuz/>

StartupFactory.uz – first Uzbekistan accelerator for IT-projects. The accelerator helps the approved teams to create a scalable and profitable startup.

<http://startupfactory.uz/accelerator/?lang=en>

Water Solution Innovation Lab Startup Accelerator is supporting startup from the next areas: clean technology, sustainable development, water purification, water and energy, water and agriculture, water/natural resource management, renewable energy sources, agriculture & agribusiness, climate change, pollution.

<http://smartwaterlab.uz/ob-akseleratore/>

Complementing the organizations mentioned so far, the subsequent figure (Figure 20.) summarizes the key supporting actors in the ecosystem.

FIGURE 19. Selection of most relevant ecosystem supporting actors.
Source: TUZ Ventures–IT Park (2021)

REMARKABLE STARTUPS:

Billz is a retail automation software that helps retail outlets reach maximum efficiency, saving a lot of time and money.

[<https://billz.uz>](https://billz.uz)

CLICK's activities are based on involvement, leadership and dedication principles. The company's mission is to make financial relations between people and companies simple, protected and reliable. CLICK.uz is a product directed to make use of money easily. You can pay all utility bills, internet, mobile communication and lots of other services by just clicking a button on your phone.

[<https://click.uz/en/about>](https://click.uz/en/about)

Express 24 is a convenient and fast food delivery service from restaurants. Order online or in a mobile application, pay by card or cash.

[<https://express24.uz/about/o-nas/>](https://express24.uz/about/o-nas/)

MyTaxi is an online platform to book taxis on-demand in Uzbekistan. Taximeter calculates the fare price and provides the receipt via the app. Users can track the location of the car on the map. Users are required to rate the journey, which affects the overall score of the driver. The app is available for both iOS and Android platforms.

[<https://mytaxi.uz/>](https://mytaxi.uz/)

OSON is the first operator of the electronic money system in Uzbekistan. Licensed by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Official partner of WebMoney, QIWI, YooMoney.

[<https://oson.uz/>](https://oson.uz/)

TASS Vision is a startup company specializing in computer vision based on artificial intelligence and cloud technologies. The company develops and implements technologies such as recognition, detection, tracking and classification, which runs on small embedded computers. In other words: A company that is essentially your third eye.

[<https://tass-vision.uz/en/>](https://tass-vision.uz/en/) [<https://www.linkedin.com/company/tassvision/>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/tassvision/)

TENDERWEEK.com is a web resource aimed at providing information on procurement announcements in Uzbekistan.

[<https://tenderweek.com/about.html>](https://tenderweek.com/about.html)

SOURCES OF THIS SUBSECTION:

enpact (2019): Startup Ecosystem Report – Tashkent. enpact e.V. data lab – Berlin, Germany.

ISBN 978-3-96604-008-2.

<https://www.enpact.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/startup-ecosystem-report-tashkent-uzbekistan.pdf>

Khoshimov, E.; Makhmudaliyev, F. (2020): Digital Transformation of Corporate Governance in Uzbekistan: Current State, Challenges and Perspectives. *International Finance and Accounting*, Vol. 2020: No. 6, Article 30.

<https://uzjournals.edu.uz/inter=nance/vol2020/iss6/30>

StartupBlink (2021): Global Map – Uzbekistan.

<https://www.startupblink.com/startups/uzbekistan>

TUZ Ventures, IT Park (2021): The Startup Ecosystem of Uzbekistan. April 2021 Report.

<https://img1.wsimg.com/blobby/go/15667cfc-6d6f-4e91-81a4-ac4243dea7c8/downloads/Uzbek%20Report%20Design%20apr15.pdf?ver=1624459228671>

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

**OUR PRIMARY
RESEARCH**

5. OUR PRIMARY RESEARCH

5.1 APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

Startup ecosystems can be analyzed from a wide variety of perspectives. It is very similar to examination fractals, the more we focus, the more detail we can learn, but full-scale mapping is almost impossible. In the case of ecosystems difficulties are exacerbated by changes in their structures over time and the lack of quality, relevant information. In our first White Paper we would like to lay only the foundation for our future work in helping startup ecosystems in their development.

Our approach can be derived from the digital transformation's needs and challenges for intelligent responses in connection with these processes.

Our research is based on the following logic:

Startup value creation processes start from the ideas, knowledge and motivations of the innovators (founders) and the brilliant workforce (talents). The value creation – due to the nature of startups – is innovative and tries to promote the success of the company and in parallel the global expansion.

We follow this line of thought, we want to examine the basic characteristics of ecosystems, startups, the supporting factors, the opinions of several ecosystem members and the challenges emerging regarding digital transformation. The next figure (Figure 21.) depicts our analytical approach.

FIGURE 21. Research approach and the most relevant factors analyzed by the survey. *Source:* own elaboration

In order to get the information needed we used an online questionnaire and conducted guided interviews with accelerators, investors and other relevant ecosystem actors in the Eurasian Startup Awards (EASA) region. This region covers 10 countries: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Russia, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan and one additional promising country, Kyrgyzstan. Hereinafter, we refer to them as EASA+1 countries. We received back almost 200 responses. As inputs we had 56 different variables and 7348 data were listed. We managed the outliers by using box-plot & 1.5 IQR method and all the necessary codings were done.

The following section covers some basic features of our focus area. E.g. location and origin of the startup, development phase, number of team members etc. (see Table 2-5.).

		FREQUENCY
Valid	Armenia	11
	Armenia, USA	1
	Azerbaijan	11
	Belarus	6
	China	2
	Cyprus	1
	Estonia	3
	Turkey, Estonia	1
	Georgia	9
	Iran	1
	Kazakhstan	10
	Moldova	2
	Netherlands	2
	Russia, Poland	1
	Russia	17
	Singapore	4
	Switzerland	1
	Turkey	33
	Ukraine	44
	Ukraine, Germany	1
Ukraine, USA	1	
USA	5	
TOTAL		167

TABLE 2. Distribution of responding startups according to their location. All listed startups have EASA region origins and the locations of branch offices are also indicated (n=167) *Source:* own research

development phase		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	formation	20	12,0	19,6	19,6
	validation	20	12,0	19,6	39,2
	growth	62	37,1	60,8	100,0
	Total	102	61,1	100,0	
Missing	999	65	38,9		
Total		167	100,0		

TABLE 3. Distribution of responding startups according to their development phase. Only available datas are included (n=102). *Source:* own research

		age of company	number of team members	number of countries, market presence	sum of raised funds (USD)
N	Valid	154	140	143	134
	Missing	13	27	24	33
Median		3,00	7,50	2	50000
Mode		2	5	1	50000
Std. Deviation		2,06	5,30	1,66	94767,94

TABLE 4. Descriptive statistics on startups. Only available datas are included.
Source: own research

age of company		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0	1	,6	,6	,6
	1	23	13,8	14,9	15,6
	2	40	24,0	26,0	41,6
	3	38	22,8	24,7	66,2
	4	18	10,8	11,7	77,9
	5	9	5,4	5,8	83,8
	6	7	4,2	4,5	88,3
	7	7	4,2	4,5	92,9
	8	9	5,4	5,8	98,7
	9	2	1,2	1,3	100,0
Total		154	92,2	100,0	

TABLE 5. Age distribution of the companies – outliers are removed.
Source: own research

As you can observe, most startups are very young, they were founded two or three years ago. The median value of team members is 7.5 and the market presence – in most cases – limited to the local markets. The next chapter, *Regional outlook* reveals all the most important factors which could affect the birth of startups, their development and the talents who are able to create new innovation and have the proper skill sets to adapt to the digital transformation.

5.2 REGIONAL OUTLOOK

We outline the most important differences focusing on innovation performance, the supporting environment and the human resource aspects (talents) regarding the digital transformation. Such indicators appear here which seem to be relevant to our subsequent analysis: Global Innovation Index, Global Talent Competitiveness Index (GTCI) main and sub-indicators, and StartupBlink's main ranking indicators.

Besides our focus countries (EASA+1 including Kyrgyzstan), we present some performance indicators of the most developed ecosystems as well. In this regard, according to StartupBlink, the top 10 countries are: USA, United Kingdom, Israel, Canada, Germany, Netherlands, Australia, Switzerland, Spain, Sweden. China and Singapore serve as an additional reference point to our dataset (StartupBlink, 2020).

In line with the Global Innovation Index scores we can state that there is a quite huge possibility for improvements. Regarding the talent indices which are spotlighted to Artificial Intelligence, digital properties of a country and talents who will drive or manage the digital transformation, the situation is much better. Based on the score values, the relative disadvantage is already smaller here, so digital specialization can induce an extremely fruitful future for the region. The only question is how this can be realized.

Country	Global Innovation Index score (0-100) median 30,94	Global Innovation Index rank (from 131)	GTCI score (INSEAD) 2020	GTCI rank (INSEAD) 2020 (from 132 countries)
Armenia (ARM)	32,64	61	43,52	60
Azerbaijan (AZE)	27,23	82	48,57	45
Belarus (BLR)	31,27	64	n.a.	n.a.
Goergia (GEO)	31,78	63	41,11	68
Kazakhstan (KAZ)	28,56	77	46,02	54
Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)	24,51	94	35,72	91
Moldova (MDA)	32,98	59	36,64	86
Russia (RUS)	35,63	47	47,07	48
Turkey (TUR)	34,9	51	38,37	78
Ukraine (UKR)	36,32	45	41,47	66
Uzbekistan (UZB)	24,54	93	n.a.	n.a.
USA	60,56	3	79,09	2
United Kingdom (UK)	59,68	4	72,27	12
Israel (ISR)	53,55	13	65,66	20
Canada (CAN)	52,26	17	71,26	13
Germany (GER)	56,55	9	72,34	11
Netherlands (NED)	58,76	5	74,99	6
Australia (AUS)	48,35	23	72,53	10
Switzerland (SUI)	66,08	1	81,26	1
Spain (ESP)	45,6	30	55,7	32
Sweden (SWE)	62,47	2	75,82	4
China (CHN)	53,28	14	49,64	42
Singapore (SGP)	56,61	8	78,48	3

TABLE 6. Main differences between top performers and the analysed ecosystems focusing on the Global Innovation Index and the Global Talent Competitiveness Index. Scores and ranks are highlighted parallelly for the year 2020.

Sources: Dutta et al. (2020) and Lanvin-Monteiro (2020)

The next tables (Table 7-11.) also provide us useful information on the EASA+1 region. The status – which serves as a starting and reference point for the further development activities – and the possible lags can be captured here as well.

Country	Ease of doing business score	R&D expenditure score	ICT infrastructure score	Technology utilisation score	Investment in emerging technologies score
Armenia (ARM)	79,96	4,67	61,58	48,58	46,26
Azerbaijan (AZE)	85,8	3,74	62,85	64,06	67,18
Belarus (BLR)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Goergia (GEO)	94,09	6,03	58,27	36,65	29,9
Kazakhstan (KAZ)	84,46	2,59	74,68	43,48	37,04
Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)	67,38	2,07	36,39	16,39	19,32
Moldova (MDA)	76,69	6,3	74,81	38,4	19,51
Russia (RUS)	83,53	23,96	70,61	52,97	48,9
Turkey (TUR)	78,1	20,76	58,78	51,73	27,62
Ukraine (UKR)	67,24	9,51	62,6	42,28	40,56
Uzbekistan (UZB)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
USA	93,14	61,1	83,84	100	100
United Kingdom (UK)	92,96	36,37	95,04	84,12	82,43
Israel (ISR)	76,13	100	82,57	95,65	96,21
Canada (CAN)	86,91	34,43	79,52	76,74	68,25
Germany (GER)	86,26	66,22	92,24	86,41	86,85
Netherlands (NED)	81,15	43,56	88,68	92,4	87,95
Australia (AUS)	88,46	41,84	80,41	75,91	65,76
Switzerland (SUI)	80,53	73,65	91,22	96,15	89,43
Spain (ESP)	84,08	26,15	80,15	62,27	43,01
Sweden (SWE)	90,5	72,29	87,4	98,63	91,97
China (CHN)	76,87	46,34	49,62	54,03	59,71
Singapore (SGP)	97,59	48,45	88,17	85,04	78,6

TABLE 7. Main differences between top performers and the analysed ecosystems focusing on the Global Talent Competitiveness Index sub-indicators: Ease of doing business, R&D expenditures, ICT infrastructure, Technology utilisation and Investment in emerging technologies. Score values are valid for the year 2020. *Source:* Lanvin–Monteiro (2020)

It is clear that there is a lack of funding for research & development in the countries of the region. As we will see later, this is one of the most important bottlenecks. The availability of ICT infrastructure, however, is quite good compared with the top performers. Focusing on technology utilization and emerging technologies we can observe significant imbalances among EASA countries.

To be aware of these circumstances and taking these characteristics into consideration will be helpful and particularly important later in formulating development and specialization strategies.

Country	Brain gain score	Lifelong Learning score	Vocational enrolment score	Tertiary education expenditure score	University ranking score
Armenia (ARM)	36,19	27,98	16,22	6,16	n.a.
Azerbaijan (AZE)	70,78	38,76	n.a.	9,58	11,71
Belarus (BLR)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Goergia (GEO)	37,01	23,95	6,58	6,74	n.a.
Kazakhstan (KAZ)	46,62	35,71	16,66	4,62	32,08
Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)	23,51	38,92	12,37	1,91	n.a.
Moldova (MDA)	13,67	30,43	22,32	22,2	n.a.
Russia (RUS)	43,43	46,02	24,46	17,62	48,21
Turkey (TUR)	23,57	28,42	38,71	35,08	24,37
Ukraine (UKR)	29,84	36,78	11,8	36,2	21,53
Uzbekistan (UZB)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
USA	94,77	92,68	n.a.	32,23	100
United Kingdom (UK)	93,19	78,42	70,64	31,37	97,03
Israel (ISR)	58,67	54,91	30,46	21,42	42,83
Canada (CAN)	82,74	77,88	7,27	38,84	79,99
Germany (GER)	78,76	75,73	29,52	29,02	71,1
Netherlands (NED)	80,82	87,06	56,09	38,76	68,32
Australia (AUS)	74,64	74,93	56,63	36,41	80,93
Switzerland (SUI)	100	100	57,92	31,17	84,21
Spain (ESP)	38,93	58,42	28,49	21,46	46,55
Sweden (SWE)	67,97	83,11	33,43	45,34	60,11
China (CHN)	66,5	70,74	29,62	n.a.	85,02
Singapore (SGP)	94,47	87,35	17,84	22,63	70,49

TABLE 8. Main differences between top performers and the analysed ecosystems focusing on the Global Talent Competitiveness Index sub-indicators: Brain gain, Lifelong learning, Vocational enrolment, Tertiary education expenditure and University ranking. Score values are valid for the year 2020. Source: Lanvin–Monteiro (2020)

In connection with tertiary education expenditures and university ranking the picture is even more heterogeneous and diverse: incomplete statistics and extreme discrepancies in values.

As universities play a crucial role in development processes and in creating/sharing knowledge, so this kind of disregard for universities can also be a serious constraint on the prosperity of startup ecosystems. A remarkable fact is that Azerbaijan in the field of brain gain (*and in brain retention too, an acceptable value can be seen*) is ahead of some top performers from Europe or other parts of the World.

Country	Quality of management schools score	Use of virtual professional networks score	Collaboration within organizations score	Collaboration across organizations score	Brain retention score
Armenia (ARM)	36,47	4,62	50,26	39,29	32,85
Azerbaijan (AZE)	47,07	2,08	64,09	65,25	67,52
Belarus (BLR)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Goergia (GEO)	36,58	5,13	47,82	29,99	35,86
Kazakhstan (KAZ)	38,55	3,55	49,84	44,29	36,05
Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)	18,75	1,11	44,27	25,87	20,57
Moldova (MDA)	28,96	n.a.	41,95	19,58	6,29
Russia (RUS)	41,59	5,22	58,47	47,77	44,26
Turkey (TUR)	25,41	15,94	39,13	38,71	27,67
Ukraine (UKR)	48,94	4,57	53,22	41,62	19,14
Uzbekistan (UZB)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
USA	88,31	79,2	96,93	100	97,76
United Kingdom (UK)	89,46	63,95	76,41	75,6	84,95
Israel (ISR)	77,19	22,91	93,92	83,58	71,8
Canada (CAN)	85,39	60,59	76,73	57,06	77,29
Germany (GER)	72,09	7,8	91,54	89,94	82,68
Netherlands (NED)	89,66	66,47	89,86	81,64	84,98
Australia (AUS)	75,39	62,25	73,32	48,33	72,3
Switzerland (SUI)	100	27,53	100	80,32	100
Spain (ESP)	79,79	37,29	36,11	31,72	38,14
Sweden (SWE)	77,73	47,34	93,72	81,08	78,8
China (CHN)	54,44	0,41	61,09	66,29	62,71
Singapore (SGP)	90,48	76,35	77,59	66,2	89,29

TABLE 9. Main differences between top performers and the analysed ecosystems focusing on the Global Talent Competitiveness Index sub-indicators: Quality of management schools, Use of virtual professional networks, Collaboration within organizations, Collaboration across organizations and Brain retention. Score values are valid for the year 2020. *Source:* Lanvin–Monteiro (2020)

In general, the score values of the quality of management schools are not so bad. We can conclude that the dissemination of a desirable entrepreneurial culture is well-founded – at least in this respect.

When we observe the collaborations within and across different organizations the picture is not disappointing at all. Later, we examine the relevance of these kinds of collaborations among ecosystem players. Regarding *brain retention* Azerbaijan, Russia, Kazakhstan and Georgia are in the most advantageous position.

Country	Relevance of education system to the economy	Workforce with tertiary education score	Availability of scientists and engineers score	Innovation output score	High-value exports score	New business density score
Armenia (ARM)	50,8	44,49	58,18	38,88	19,27	8,32
Azerbaijan (AZE)	61,19	40,01	70,43	21,72	5,81	4,92
Belarus (BLR)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Goergia (GEO)	31,33	51,42	22,69	33,98	8,84	40,29
Kazakhstan (KAZ)	41,96	52,78	41,94	20,84	67,6	10,77
Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)	32,56	26,91	30,41	15,59	25,92	6,08
Moldova (MDA)	36,01	36,16	23,41	41,86	15,32	8,41
Russia (RUS)	46,32	77,72	60,14	34,5	34,31	20,88
Turkey (TUR)	28,22	35,41	39,66	38,88	7,53	5,63
Ukraine (UKR)	47,98	80,84	61,54	48,51	14,82	7,39
Uzbekistan (UZB)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
USA	96,93	72,02	100	80,91	41,15	n.a.
United Kingdom (UK)	68,53	64,85	76,74	84,06	61,67	75,81
Israel (ISR)	64,76	51,98	83,2	79,16	41,22	16,51
Canada (CAN)	78,62	100	85,84	61,3	38,27	0,26
Germany (GER)	81,05	43,51	80,5	78,28	41,4	6,23
Netherlands (NED)	83,99	55,25	71,22	89,49	55,32	29,22
Australia (AUS)	70,24	57,48	73,19	52,36	38,09	74,69
Switzerland (SUI)	100	61,86	81,44	100	32,72	20,71
Spain (ESP)	40,25	60,2	63,13	56,04	20,97	15,51
Sweden (SWE)	73,21	61,91	75,38	88,44	37,16	38,95
China (CHN)	63,76	n.a.	68,58	81,26	70,91	n.a.
Singapore (SGP)	91,96	82,7	80,63	66,9	100	41,51

TABLE 10. Main differences between top performers and the analysed ecosystems focusing on the Global Talent Competitiveness Index sub-indicators: Relevance of education system to the economy, Workforce with tertiary education, Availability of scientists and engineers, Innovation output, High-value exports and New business density. Score values are valid for the year 2020. Source: Lanvin–Monteiro (2020)

Let's see the high-quality inputs, the high-quality outputs of innovation and the vibrancy of the business sector. There are well performing countries in our focus region regarding workforce with tertiary education. Ukraine, Russia are on the top, while the others significantly lag behind. The two, previously mentioned countries are also outstanding globally. They are ahead of most countries listed among top ecosystems. In addition to the contributing effects of other factors, thanks to the good brain gain & brain retention positions in Azerbaijan the availability of scientists and engineers is outstanding. Ukraine, Moldova, Turkey, Armenia and Russian are the innovation leaders in our region regarding the output side (innovation output and high-value export). The most vibrant business environment can be found in Georgia with nearly twice as much value as the country in second place.

Country & largest startup ecosystem	StartupBlink total score (2020) national (highest score 123,167)	StartupBlink largest ecosystem (2020) global rank (from 1000 cities)	StartupBlink total score (2020) largest ecosystem
Armenia (ARM) Yerevan	1,829	209	1,131
Azerbaijan (AZE) Baku	0,539	323	0,536
Belarus (BLR) Minsk	1,038	197	1,258
Goergia (GEO) Tbilisi	0,408	396	0,384
Kazakhstan (KAZ) Almaty	0,233	520	0,229
Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Moldova (MDA) Chisinau	0,906	284	0,653
Russia (RUS) Moscow	8,524	9	22,055
Turkey (TUR) Istanbul	3,166	80	4,877
Ukraine (UKR) Kiev	5,057	32	9,712
Uzbekistan (UZB) Tashkent	n.a.	966	0,066
USA San Francisco	123,167	1	225,31
United Kingdom London	24,406	3	48,39
Israel Tel-Aviv	19,408	7	23,789
Canada Toronto	17,72	24	12,082
Germany Berlin	13,77	8	22,345
Netherlands Amsterdam	13,053	20	14,223
Australia Sydney	11,98	31	10,84
Switzerland Zurich	11,323	65	5,349
Spain Barcelona	10,822	27	11,752
Sweden Stockholm	10,77	29	11,338
China Beijing	8,972	6	25,519
Singapore	8,569	26	11,966

TABLE 11. Main differences between top performers and the analysed ecosystems focusing on the StartupBlink national scores and the global rank and score of the largest ecosystem in the given country. Values are valid for the year 2020. Source: StartupBlink (2020)

When we examine the general performance and success of different startup ecosystems we can identify the supremacy of Russia, Ukraine and Turkey.

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

**KEY RESULTS
& TAKEAWAYS**

6. KEY RESULTS & TAKEAWAYS

This chapter contains the most important result of our survey. The presentation of the outputs follow the research logic of this paper.

6.1 TALENTS

The subsequent tables (Table 12-17.) summarize the opinions of our respondents on the importance and contribution of the talented workforce to the innovation performance of their own startups.

		innovation number of workforce		innovation digital skills		innovation digital technologies at hand	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	4,6	4,6	1,5	1,5	3,1	3,1
	slightly important	12,3	16,9	4,6	6,2	7,7	10,8
	moderately important	30,8	47,7	21,5	27,7	29,2	40,0
	very important	29,2	76,9	27,7	55,4	24,6	64,6
	extremely important	23,1	100,0	44,6	100,0	35,4	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 12. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different „talent“ factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization (n=102). Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5). *Source:* own research

		innovation team competencies		innovation creativity of workforce		workforce lexical knowledge by universities	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	9,2	9,2
	slightly important	3,1	4,6	6,2	7,7	7,7	16,9
	moderately important	13,8	18,5	16,9	24,6	35,4	52,3
	very important	33,8	52,3	33,8	58,5	23,1	75,4
	extremely important	47,7	100,0	41,5	100,0	24,6	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 13. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different „talent“ factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization (n=102). Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5).

Source: own research

		workforce practical experience by universities		workforce international experience		workforce real english language skills	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	4,6	4,6	3,1	3,1	0,0	0,0
	slightly important	6,2	10,8	3,1	6,2	1,5	1,5
	moderately important	20,0	30,8	12,3	18,5	9,2	10,8
	very important	33,8	64,6	29,2	47,7	26,2	36,9
	extremely important	35,4	100,0	52,3	100,0	63,1	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 14. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different „talent“ factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization (n=102). Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5).

Source: own research

		workforce other language skills		workforce creativity		workforce learning and adaptive skills	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	1,5	1,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	slightly important	12,3	13,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	moderately important	32,3	46,2	16,9	16,9	7,7	7,7
	very important	29,2	75,4	27,7	44,6	16,9	24,6
	extremely important	24,6	100,0	55,4	100,0	75,4	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 15. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different „talent“ factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization (n=102). Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5).

Source: own research

		workforce precise work		workforce team competencies		workforce proactive attitudes	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	slightly important	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	0,0	0,0
	moderately important	12,3	13,8	10,8	12,3	3,1	3,1
	very important	36,9	50,8	26,2	38,5	32,3	35,4
	extremely important	49,2	100,0	61,5	100,0	64,6	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 16. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different „talent“ factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization (n=102). Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5).

Source: own research

		workforce loyalty		workforce cultural fit	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	slightly important	1,5	1,5	6,2	6,2
	moderately important	10,8	12,3	13,8	20,0
	very important	35,4	47,7	30,8	50,8
	extremely important	52,3	100,0	49,2	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0	

TABLE 17. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different „talent“ factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization (n=102). Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5).

Source: own research

After reviewing the data, it can be stated that the general expectations on the workforce are in line with the latest approach to human resource management that focuses on the special nature of nonlinear organizations.

We can set up a rank order to see and understand the cumulative opinions about the importance of workforce (talents) (see Table 18. on the next page).

evaluation factors	extremely important (5)(%)	evaluation factors	extremely important (5) & very important (4) together (%)
number of workforce	23,1	lexical knowledge provided by universities for the workforce	47,7
lexical knowledge provided by universities for the workforce	24,6	number of workforce	52,3
other language skills	24,6	other language skills	53,8
practical experience provided by universities for the workforce	35,4	practical experience provided by universities for the workforce	69,2
creativity of workforce	41,5	digital skills	72,3
digital skills	44,6	creativity of workforce	75,3
team competencies	47,7	cultural fit	80
precise work	49,2	team competencies	81,5
cultural fit	49,2	international experience	81,5
international experience	52,3	workforce creativity	83,1
workforce loyalty	52,3	precise work	86,1
workforce creativity	55,4	workforce loyalty	87,7
real english language skills	63,1	real english language skills	89,3
proactive attitudes	64,6	learning and adaptive skills	92,3
learning and adaptive skills	75,4	proactive attitudes	96,9

TABLE 18. Rank orders of the cumulated opinions about the importance of workforce in the innovation processes of a given startup. Values are in ascending order and expressed in percentages (n=102). *Source:* own research

Reading through the content of the table the following findings can be made:

If we look only at only the *extremely important* evaluation, the top three factors are: (1st) learning and adaptive skills, (2nd) proactive attitudes and (3rd) real english language skills. When we add the *extremely important* and *very important* together (Likert scale 4 & 5) the situation changes somewhat: First is the proactive attitudes,

second is the learning and adaptive skills and in the third place is the real english language skills.

The least important factors are – according to the logic described above:

(15th) number of workforce, (14th) lexical knowledge provided by universities and (13th) other language skills.

The extended version (Likert scale 4&5 together) presents us the following results:

(15th) lexical knowledge provided by universities, (14th) number of workforce and (13th) other language skills.

6.2 ECOSYSTEM

In this chapter we explore the most important opinions and verdicts on the supportive startup ecosystems.

The next tables (Table 19-20.) point out the evaluations on startup ecosystem contributions to internal, organizational innovation.

		innovation - supportive culture		innovation - local market conditions		innovation - global market conditions	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	1,5	1,5	6,2	6,2	1,5	1,5
	slightly important	4,6	6,2	16,9	23,1	10,8	12,3
	moderately important	30,8	36,9	20	43,1	20,0	32,2
	very important	27,7	64,6	33,8	76,9	35,4	67,7
	extremely important	35,4	100,0	23,1	100,0	32,3	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 19. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different ecosystem factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization. Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5) (n=102).

Source: own research

Interesting is that the supportive culture, the local market and global market conditions, the support from the local ecosystem (in general) and the governmental support are not rated as important as we have seen in the case of some talent indicators (see Table 18. above).

		innovation - support from local ecosystem (in general)		innovation - governmental support (ecosystem actor)	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all important	12,3	12,3	21,5	21,5
	slightly important	15,4	27,7	20,0	41,5
	moderately important	30,8	58,5	32,3	73,8
	very important	21,5	80,0	16,9	90,8
	extremely important	20,0	100,0	9,2	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0	

TABLE 20. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the importance of different ecosystem factors influencing the innovation performance of the specific organization. Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5) (n=102).
Source: own research

The following tables (Table 21-22.) show the distribution of the respondents' evaluation on different attributes of their ecosystem.

		ecosystem - networking opportunities		ecosystem - support from other players		ecosystem events	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	very poor	6,2	6,2	12,3	12,3	4,6	4,6
	below average	10,8	16,9	20,0	32,3	10,8	15,4
	average	20,0	36,9	20,0	52,3	30,8	46,2
	above average	27,7	64,6	24,6	76,9	29,2	75,4
	excellent	35,4	100,0	23,1	100,0	24,6	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 21. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the supportive ecosystem. Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5) (n=102). *Source:* own research

		ecosystem - fundraising possibilities		ecosystem - special advantages		ecosystem flow of information and knowledge	
		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	very poor	21,5	21,5	13,8	13,8	3,1	3,1
	below average	16,9	38,5	13,8	27,7	10,8	13,8
	average	36,9	75,4	30,8	58,5	27,7	41,5
	above average	12,3	87,7	18,5	76,9	32,3	73,8
	excellent	12,3	100,0	23,1	100,0	26,2	100,0
	Total	100,0		100,0		100,0	

TABLE 22. Distribution of responding startups' evaluations on the supportive ecosystem. Results are based on Likert-scale values (1-5) (n=102). *Source:* own research

The networking opportunities factor is top rated, while the fundraising possibilities offered by the ecosystem is the most undervalued.

6.3 MARKET PRESENCE AND THE GLOBAL EXPANSION

Expanding market presence is one of the most important adventures in the life of a startup. In most cases the development processes induce increasing market potential. During the analysis we not only focused on the whole region as a monolithic block, but also we tried to form more heterogeneous groups as well. We found that a geopolitical categorization could be a proper solution. In this regard three groups of countries were delineated: Turkic Council member states, Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS countries) and South Caucasus countries.

The following section will discuss the market presence and the issues of global expansion in accordance with this classification. Turkic Council states in our study: Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkey and Uzbekistan; CIS countries: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia and Uzbekistan; South Caucasus countries: Armenia, Azerbaijan and Georgia.

The subsequent tables (Table 23-25.) summarize for us the market presence of the above introduced three groups of countries. Three larger regions were selected to see the market penetration processes: USA and Canada, Asia, Europe.

		USA, CAN presence		Total
		no	yes	
Turkic Council member	non	77	34	111
	yes	37	17	54
Total		114	51	165

		USA, CAN presence		Total
		no	yes	
CIS member	non	71	37	108
	yes	43	15	58
Total		114	52	166

		USA, CAN presence		Total
		no	yes	
South Caucasus	non	89	45	134
	yes	25	7	32
Total		114	52	166

TABLE 23. Market presence of the Turkic Council member states, the CIS members and the South Caucasus countries in USA & Canada (n=165, 166).

Source: own research

In terms of percentage shares the Turkic Council member states have the largest market penetration rate (31,48%). So, nearly one third of the startups surveyed are already present in the region (USA and Canada). CIS countries have 25,86%, and South Caucasus countries' similar value is 21,87%.

		Asia presence		Total
		no	yes	
Turkic Council member	non	82	28	110
	yes	39	15	54
Total		121	43	164

		Asia presence		Total
		no	yes	
CIS member	non	82	25	107
	yes	40	18	58
Total		122	43	165

		Asia presence		Total
		no	yes	
South Caucasus	non	94	39	133
	yes	28	4	32
Total		122	43	165

TABLE 24. Market presence of the Turkic Council member states, the CIS members and the South Caucasus countries in Asia (n=164, 165). *Source:* own research

Here, the percentages of the market penetration rates are as follows:

Turkic Council members: 27,77%;

CIS countries: 31,03%;

South Caucasus countries: 12,5%.

		Europe presence		Total
		no	yes	
Turkic Council member	non	70	41	111
	yes	30	24	54
Total		100	65	165

		Europe presence		Total
		no	yes	
CIS member	non	55	53	108
	yes	45	13	58
Total		100	66	166

		Europe presence		Total
		no	yes	
South Caucasus	non	71	63	134
	yes	29	3	32
Total		100	66	166

TABLE 25. Market presence of the Turkic Council member states, the CIS members and the South Caucasus countries in Europe (n=165, 166). *Source:* own research

Regarding the Table 24., the percentages of the market penetration rates are as follows:

Turkic Council members: 44,44%;

CIS countries: 22,41%;

South Caucasus countries: 9,37%.

It seems that the South Caucasus countries have the most difficulties or are not so successful in market expansion.

The table below (Table 26.) show us the planned, desired market expansion destinations of the three groups of countries.

		Geographical expansion									Total
		no plan for expansion	Eurasia	Europe	North Africa	United Kingdom	Asia	Global expansion	USA, Canada	Latin America	
Turkic Council member	non	0	10	23	1	7	11	2	11	1	66
	yes	1	7	20	0	1	5	0	2	0	36
Total		1	17	43	1	8	16	2	13	1	102

		Geographical expansion									Total
		no plan for expansion	Eurasia	Europe	North Africa	United Kingdom	Asia	Global expansion	USA, Canada	Latin America	
CIS member	non	1	7	27	1	8	10	0	8	0	62
	yes	0	10	16	0	0	6	2	5	1	40
Total		1	17	43	1	8	16	2	13	1	102

		Geographical expansion									Total
		no plan for expansion	Eurasia	Europe	North Africa	United Kingdom	Asia	Global expansion	USA, Canada	Latin America	
South Caucasus	non	1	11	32	1	8	16	2	9	0	81
	yes	0	6	11	0	0	0	0	4	1	21
Total		1	17	43	1	8	16	2	13	1	102

TABLE 26. Desired market expansion destinations of Turkic Council member states, CIS countries and South Caucasus countries (n=102). *Source:* own research

According to Table 26. Europe is the most wanted target market. As we have already mentioned, the appearance on the European market is a challenge for most startups in our focus region. The next section refers to challenges including the former one as well.

6.4 CHALLENGES

Here, we present only the firstly mentioned challenges which were indicated by our respondents. Other related topics and approaches are also discussed in the full version, containing the concentrated, synthesized interview results. The following tables (Table 27–29.) demonstrate the structure, distribution of the firstly mentioned (considered most important by startups) challenges affecting the startups' growth

and development focusing on Turkic Council member states, CIS countries and South Caucasus countries. All the answers were provided by startups.

		Firstly mentioned challenge						Total
		investment	market conditions, structure of demand	revenue	human capital, talent	technology	knowledge	
Turkic Council member	non	48	31	9	8	5	6	107
	yes	23	13	8	5	1	1	51
Total		71	44	17	13	6	7	158

TABLE 27. Distribution of the firstly mentioned (most important) startup challenges in connection with growth and development in Turkic Council member states (n=158). *Source:* own research

		Firstly mentioned challenge						Total
		investment	market conditions, structure of demand	revenue	human capital, talent	technology	knowledge	
CIS member	non	45	31	9	8	5	5	103
	yes	26	14	8	5	1	2	56
Total		71	45	17	13	6	7	159

TABLE 28. Distribution of the firstly mentioned (most important) startup challenges in connection with growth and development in CIS member states (n=159). *Source:* own research

		Firstly mentioned challenge						Total
		investment	market conditions, structure of demand	revenue	human capital, talent	technology	knowledge	
South Caucasus	non	54	40	16	9	4	5	128
	yes	17	5	1	4	2	2	31
Total		71	45	17	13	6	7	159

TABLE 29. Distribution of the firstly mentioned (most important) startup challenges in connection with growth and development in South Caucasus states (n=159). *Source:* own research

As we can observe in all countries (groups of countries), the most important challenge is to find proper sources of investment and funding. In the second place is the market conditions & demand structure, including market penetration problems too. The revenue is in the third place in the case of Turkic Council member states and CIS member states, while regarding South Caucasus countries the human capital & talent factor can be mentioned.

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

INTERVIEWS

7. INTERVIEWS

We also conducted guided professional interviews during our research. Among our interviewees were key players in the innovation ecosystems of our focus countries. We were curious about how they see the problems and challenges of ecosystems based on their professional experience. Below are the opinions of respondents involved in startup incubation and acceleration. The most important and interesting parts of each interview are presented according to the structure and order of the original questions. After a brief introduction to the organization and/or respondent, the questions focus on the following main topics: activities and general opinions about the startup ecosystem. The answers appear either literally (in the form of a question and answer), or highlighting the substance in an aggregated manner. The interviews are presented in alphabetical order

7.1 ADVICERA (UKR)

Name of the interviewee: Yuri Kozik

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/in/iurii-kozik/>>

EASA jury member, Advicera (CEO), the master of AI

Comment: He used to work at incubator Demium <<https://demium.com>> as a Head of Incubation, now he runs his own advisory company, aiming for entrepreneurs.

Advicera is a software platform helping organisations to deliver mentorship to entrepreneurs and startups founders. We offer a simple and impactful tool helping to engage and execute effective mentoring of startup founders.

Being founded by people with diverse international startup experience, Advicera is committed to improve the global entrepreneurship ecosystem and make it easier to help entrepreneurs launch tech companies.

<<https://advicera.org/>> <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/advicera-org/>>

Advicera manages ca. 50–60 startups with a special focus on B2B startups, FinTech, HealthTech and deep tech. They are in different stages because they have experts from many stages and areas.

During the selection processes for the program the company does not pay attention to the country of establishment, rather on the country the startups want to enter. Regarding the founders, coachability is the most important selection factor.

Anyway the above listed characteristics are decisive:

- the team (skills, knowledge, attitudes, structure of the team, etc.) - *Advicera mostly works with CEOs and founders,*
- the industry in which the startup operates (AI, digital transformation, IoT, e-commerce, other) - *B2B, any can come, even aerospace*
- the product/service itself - *scalable but not necessary, more viable the better,*

Currently Advicera manages a startup from Norway, so they are open for foreign startups as well.

Do you recognize any differences between the local startups and the foreign ones? If yes, then what do you think? What can be the reasons?

A: Startups from less developed ecosystems are more hungry for more knowledge. In Norway for example it's harder to reach out for someone or reach out to experts.

What does your mentor pool look like?

Advicera is connected with around a 100 experts now.

GENERAL VIEW/OPINION ON LOCAL ECOSYSTEM:

What are the main differences between this region and the currently well developed regions (startups-wise) and what could be the potential to reach such a level or get closer to them?

When it comes to specifics there is a huge gap. If they want to launch aerospace then it is very hard in less developed countries or if they want to launch their product in the USA. Internationalization opportunity - that is one of the main differences.

Steps for development: having more international connection and international knowledge.

Is there anything (IT talent, funding, etc.) that this ecosystem can offer which is at the same level or even higher than the current well developed ones?

Tech talent for sure.

What are the obstacles for startups with great potential that the system holds in?

Not enough experts and knowledge regarding international markets.

What is your opinion on education (startup-wise)?

Few changes happened recently. There is for sure progress, but now it's just general methodology.

What and how do you contribute to the development of it?

Online webinars, workshops (before COVID - offline)

How do you see universities doing in this field? Are they active?

There are some activities, but the outcome is not that visible.

What is your experience: Do startups want/willing to open to the EU's/other region's markets?

Yes, absolutely.

Specifically, what part of the world?

Number one market is the USA. But there are some interested in the EU (Central and Eastern part but also included Germany) and UK as well.

What are the biggest obstacles?

Understanding how to work with these countries, how the industry looks like, what are the habits of the customers etc.

How can you help them?

with the help of networking and social capital

Do you have any connection with EU/or other regional HUBs, Incubators, Accelerators?

Yes, we have. Not official but non formal in Finland and Norway.

7.2 GENERATIONS (RUS)

Name of the organization: GenerationS

<https://en.generation-startup.ru/>

Managing director: Ekaterina Petrova

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/petrovaekaterina/>

GenerationS represents a platform for corporate innovations development; it is the largest corporate accelerator across Russia and CIS. Established by Russian Venture Company, RVC JSC in 2013.

GenerationS implements comprehensive corporation development programs including in-house programs for intrapreneurship development, acceleration programs for scouting and external project acceleration, and international programs for staff training in innovations development and management methods based on international leading corporations.

The mission of the organization is to create a mature venture capital market through the consolidation and development of resources, competencies and initiatives on the part of investors, investment portfolio managers and entrepreneurs so as to create and promote innovative products and technologies in priority technology areas, making Russia a leader in the global technology market.

They are currently industry centric, their recent programs were on retail tech, agtech, metals and mining, power sector, transport and mobility, FMCG, pharma etc. GenerationS is working actively with foreign startups, it also depends on the needs of their corporate partners within their corporate acceleration programs or corporate pilots programs.

Main benefits for foreign startups and what they can get from GenerationS:

- paid pilot – an opportunity to launch a paid pilot project with a corporate partner,
- expertise – startups will receive in-depth feedback on the product or solution from the leading industrial experts,
- scaling – if a pilot is successful, startups will have an opportunity to integrate solutions in corporate partners business-processes and infrastructure,
- corporate access – access to and potential cooperation with other Russian companies.

Since 2018 more than 300 international startups from more than 30 countries applied to take part in GenerationS programs with such corporate partners as Ilim, Ferring, Enel, PepsiCo, GTLK, Chelpipe, Lenta etc.

For now, GenerationS has around 20 international alumni startups who passed the programs and are partnering with corporates to realize various projects. Among GenerationS international alumni startups we have tech companies from Belarus, Estonia, Finland, Sweden and USA.

GenerationS does not invest in startups and does not take any equity. The programs are free of charges for startups and our corporate partners usually provide funding for pilot projects.

What are the main differences between this region and the currently well developed (startups-wise) regions and what could be the potential to reach such a level or get closer to them?

In 2020, Moscow entered the top 10 world cities with the best startup ecosystems, moving up four ranks compared to 2017. San Francisco was ranked first, followed by New York and London. Some other Russian cities increased their positions in the rating, for example, Irkutsk (+61), Perm (+57) and Saint-Petersburg (+52). In the overall rating Russia moved up 3 positions and took the 15th position. (according to Startup Blink).

The Russian market is quite attractive for international startups in terms of increasing domestic demand which is the main driving force of economic growth. Also, the most attractive indicators for the international startups are the large market size, high level of ICT adoption and human capital.

Now, the Russian government has identified R&D spending and innovation development as a strategic priority: large enterprises are incentivized to work with tech entrepreneurs in a way that fosters the ecosystem. Russian corporations are becoming more active in this sphere and are externalising R&D.

Is there anything (IT talent, funding, etc.) that this ecosystem can offer which is at the same level or even higher than the current well developed ones?

The tech ecosystem is varied, diverse, widespread and has a large number of network players. Improvement of the business environment, conditions for doing business and startup institutions have been another focus of innovation policy in recent years. As a result, an entrepreneurial infrastructure was created in all senses of the word – territorial, financial, informational, and regulatory.

Each organization uses in its activity a certain set of tools – those with direct action (grants, subsidies, loans, etc.), indirect action (various benefits) as well as organizational and legal tools (international collaboration, stimulation of demand, provision of infrastructure, etc.).

Priority areas obviously include financial support, the provision of infrastructure, consulting and information support.

What are the obstacles for startups with great potential that the system holds in?

- 1. science and innovation culture has not evolved to value strong business skills,*
- 2. much of Russia's private sector is highly concentrated, with a small number of large companies that have neither the objectives to cultivate tech entrepreneurship nor the necessary understanding of the requirements to do so. This reduces the prospects for young tech companies in terms of market entry, partnerships and exit options investment, and acquisitions,*
- 3. rigid regulatory environment.*

What is your experience: Do startups want/willing to open to the EU's/other region's markets?

Yes, startups generally are open to the EU's/other region's markets?

Startups register their companies abroad to leverage more established legal, investment, and dispute resolution frameworks.

What are the biggest obstacles?

Language and soft-skills.

Do you have any connection with EU/or other regional HUBs, incubators, accelerators?

Yes, we have more than 450 international partners worldwide.

What are the tangible results of such cooperation?

GenerationS, as part of the international innovation ecosystem, facilitates the promotion of its alumni in foreign markets.

- 65% share of foreign investment*
- 73 alumni sell abroad*
- 28+ alumni passed foreign acceleration programs*

Alumni development geography. The alumni develop their business in 42 countries worldwide

- 17% - USA
- 35% - CIS
- 30% - Europe
- 5% - Middle East
- 13% - Asia

7.3 IBA INNOVATION CENTER (AZE)

Name of the interviewee: Zaur Alakbarov

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/in/zaur-alakbarov-b8474621/>>

Adviser to CEO of The International Bank of Azerbaijan

Name of the organization: IBA Innovation Center, Azerbaijan, Baku

Founder: The International Bank of Azerbaijan which is a governmental organization

The **IBA Innovation Center** is mainly sponsored by the Government. Members and executives of the program have extended skills and practices. They have professionals with academic knowledge, entrepreneurial and business development skills, also over 10 years of work experience of digital transformations in the IT sphere both in private and governmental sectors and in the Bank sphere. Besides this, they continuously work with international hands-on professional consultants and coaches.

The International Bank of Azerbaijan supports this program - Startups in their business development both with external consulting companies by coaching and mentoring and with professional internal staff. But, it doesn't invest in startups' capital requirements.

The IBA Innovation Center also contributes to the development of startups. Thus, a total of 99 projects were submitted to the Incubation Program announced in the second half of 2020. 48 of all teams have 48 passed to the second stage, and 12 relevant projects out of 48 were selected in the final stage. IBA Innovation Center offers incubation and acceleration programs as well.

The IBA Innovation Center, as the founder of many innovative projects in 2019–2020, has contributed and continues to contribute to the development of the ecosystem. The IBA Innovation Center has been operating since 2019, and up today continues its services with 4 large-scale and sustainable projects and works on new projects.

Free education at the ABB Tech Academy has contributed to the success of 300 young people and has provided employment to more than 150 young people, and continues to create new opportunities. The Center organized a regional hackathon and awarded 1-2-3 places among the participants with a cash prize. These teams have applied for the Startup Incubation Program after the Hackaton. The Center contributes and stimulates professional development in building the business profiles of 12 startup projects by accepting them to the incubation phase. It is also planned to develop Fintech Startups and take them to the Acceleration phase in the next stages.

What is the general selection process of the applicants for your program? Which factors are the most relevant to the selection? Please, list 3 or 5 of them in order of importance!

- *we are mostly interested in Fintech Startups, and ideas that can give added value solutions for our organisation's further digital transformation and strategic plans.*
- *founders personal and professional skills, attitude and availability for the full commitment to the development of the business/startup are very important (soft skills) factors in the selection process.*
- *relevant professional skills, personal skills, relevant knowledge in the sphere, attitudes, commitment and collaboration of the team members are main factors in the selection process.*
- *the industry in which the startup operates (AI, digital transformation, IoT, e-commerce, financial services etc.)*

Are you looking forward to having foreign startups as well? Have you had any before? Are you currently having? From which country?

We had such a practice, a startup team from Turkey was a participant and we are always ready to accept foreign startups.

Do you recognize any differences between the local ones and the foreign ones? If yes, then what do you think? What can be the reasons?

The local ecosystem is developing every day. We have quite good start-up teams and even active investors. Every day we are convinced that we are developing more

and more in this area. With the participation of foreign teams, we are faced with a new practice for us, which was to be expected. We didn't feel a strong difference between the local ones and the foreign ones in this area. Since we work with foreign mentors, our adaptation process took place very quickly (learning process). And so we were able to complement all our flaws along the way.

What does your mentor pool look like? Where are your mentors coming from?

- Internal professional IBA staff helps in validation of business ideas (almost all startups are fintech), legal and financial support, technical & product development support,

As well IBA innovation Center has a Tech Academy we provide them resources/ team-mates with relevant technical skills if there is a need,

- Consultants with a hands-on practice located in different countries such as USA, Turkey,
- Consultants with both internal and external practice in startup and business development.

What else do you provide apart from know-how and network? Are you investing in your own startups? Maybe co-investing?

Yes. Teams formed as startups after the hackathon organized by the IBA Innovation Center at the beginning of the year were also able to participate by submitting their projects to the Incubation Program. Startups are currently undergoing an incubation phase. Teams receive training from local and foreign trainers with international experience, learning how to develop their projects on Business, Marketing, Legal and, most importantly, Technical areas of Startups, which steps to take in this direction, in what form and sequence.

How much do you usually invest?

As an Innovation Center, we don't invest in Startups capital requirements. But we have an IBA Investor Club regarding its terms and conditions. The club member which is interested in one or another startup, will invest not less than the minimum required amount.

How much equity do you usually ask for?

Each team, having determined their business capital based on their needs and requirements, forms a certain equity and we provide them to investors. The equity is different depending on the teams.

GENERAL VIEW/OPINION ON LOCAL ECOSYSTEM

What are the main differences between this region and the currently well developed (startups-wise) regions and what could be the potential to reach such a level or get closer to them?

Azerbaijan is a fairly developed country. Our country always supports and actively participates in all innovations. It is very affordable to develop in such a country precisely in this ecosystem.

Is there anything (IT talent, funding, etc.) that this ecosystem can offer that is at the same level or even higher than the current well developed ones?

We have a lot of talents in many spheres, especially IT Sphere is one of the well developed and progressing ones. Both governmental and private sectors have big challenges in digital transformation and a lot of innovative initiatives that provide youth with a chance to engage, involve and to succeed in these projects.

What are the obstacles for startups with great potential that the system holds in?

In some cases market maturity and regulation in the implementation of the new trends in banking especially in open banking, BAAP and in the other related directions can be an obstacle. But ecosystem players as we, and the government's initiatives and strategic plans promise to have an opportunity in the nearest future to be one of the leading disruptive innovators and digitized countries in the region and to have a place on the list of well developed countries.

What is your opinion on education (startup-wise)?

Most universities, especially private schools, have their own ideation labs/centers, incubation programs, and other similar centers. They are interested in formulating, and establishing entrepreneurial mindset, and ecosystem players such as we are supporting them in these initiatives.

What and how do you contribute to the development of it?

We are interested in collaboration with local universities. Establishment of joint R&D centres based on new strategic directions of the Bank and the country at the Universities is one of the initiatives in 2021. Already started negotiations with ADA University. We believe that cohesive collaboration of businesses and education spheres is very important for increasing the quality of both. Students will have an opportunity to be up-to-date, companies will have a fresh eye and view in their businesses and both of them will be above the line.

What is your experience: Do startups want/willing to open to the EU's/other region's markets?

No doubt all our Startups in long term want to open to the other markets

Specifically, what part of the world?

It depends on the product and business. For example: USA, Europe, Central Asian Countries etc.

Specifically, which part of the EU/which countries?

Eastern and western Europe countries are in the first list.

What are the biggest obstacles?

Taking into account that ecosystem development is at an early stage, our startups in most cases have difficulties in fund-raising, implementing their business ideas and generating revenue. The main reason is local investors' investment habits and their mindset, also not so matured in the local market. All these together can be defined as obstacles.

How can you help them?

Our program provides individual support to each Startup. We helped to validate, develop and scale their business ideas as well as team members' professional skills. Joining our program, young entrepreneurs met successful people, became a member of the well-known and huge community, and all these factors can turn into the guarantee of success in the long term.

Do you have any connection with EU/or other regional HUBs, Incubators, Accelerators?

We have collaboration with 2 consulting companies from Turkey with hands-on practice in Europe and the USA, and this helps our program to compare different market strategies to be aware of know-how practices and implement possible ones.

7.4 MTS STARTUP HUB (RUS)

Name of the interviewee: Olesya Kostrykina

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/in/kostrykinao/>>

Name of the organization: MTS Startup Hub <<https://startup.mts.ru/?lang=en>>

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/mtsstartuphub/>>

EASA: Jury member

MTS Startup Hub enables startups to get directly in touch with MTS – the largest Telco company in Russia with additionally 11 non-telco business units such as banking.

GENERAL EXPERIENCE IN STARTUPS

In Moscow there has been an increased number of accelerators and incubators in the recent 2–3 years. Universities and Big Corporations often have their own accelerator programme. They choose a startup to work with on Demo Day.

In general there are less opportunities for investments compared to Baltic region. In addition, other challenges should be addressed: more international focus is needed, startups don't speak English and the lack of teaching materials in English and in Russian. Mentioning the challenges of accelerators the following topics are highlighted: they have the same startups and same incubators, one of the startups finishes one program and then gets to another one. You see the same startups over and over again.

Regarding (startup-wise) education at universities there are some programs (including governmental initiatives as well) and in these cases the programs are for free. A non Moscow-centric startup ecosystem development would be necessary.

7.5 OPEN DATA INCUBATOR (UKR)

Name of the interviewee: Jane Klepa

Nationality: Ukrainian (Kiev)

Name of the organization: Open Data incubator (CEO)
<<http://1991.vc/en/main-page/>>

EASA: Jury member

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/in/jane-klepa-98ba1a93/>>

1991 Open Data Incubator (est. 1991) is a portfolio project of civic tech NGO SocialBoost. 1991 Open Data Incubator, is Ukraine's first nonprofit incubator to help turn tons of open data into real startups that provide services to citizens, businesses and government agencies.

1991 operates with support from international donors, governmental institutions and businesses. SocialBoost story roots in 2012 with a series of hackathons, dedicated to creating digital services based on open government data. In the first three years, we held 10 nationwide hackathons and a series of regional events. More than 1,000 people joined SocialBoost activities. They generated 800 ideas, over 20 projects got funding.

The main challenge is the development of an open data ecosystem. SocialBoost launched this process in 2014. They have created the National Open Data Portal on the basis of dKAN data.gov.ua, conducted an advocacy campaign on open data law, created interagency groups on open data and organized a series of training for civil servants.

Social Boost is a non-governmental organization that has been operating in Ukraine since 2011, bringing together the community of startups and the public sector to solve the national problems facing Ukraine by creating innovative projects and e-services.

In 2016–2020, 21 incubation and acceleration programs, 170 startup graduates, 40% of which received funding of more than USD 2 million in grants and investments.

How many startups are you incubating/accelerating right now?

Almost 200. Fintech, e-comm, insurance, some AI but more for analytical platforms and Big Data. Also legal tech startups.

Pre-seed and seed stage. But some are super early with ideas. They have an open call and anyone can apply.

What does your mentor pool look like? Where are your mentors coming from?

- *Corporate environment - yes*
- *Veteran entrepreneurs - yes*
- *VCs, Angels - yes*
- *other - yes*

Regarding mentors: some of them are themselves and some are “outsiders” around 90 people. They are coming from many different fields.

What is the general selection process of the applicants for your program? Which factors are the most relevant to the selection? Please, list 3 or 5 of them in order of importance!

They have stages for selection: 1. Online application 2. Interviews with the team 3. Final stage with the shortlist - 1-2days event where they see how coachable they are and then they select the best ones (10 best teams).

During selection processes the subsequent factors were taken into consideration:

- *country of establishment, - Ukrainian,*
- *country of the focus market, - It doesn't matter really, the first stage should be in Ukraine.*
- *the founders (skills, network, attitudes...) -*
- *the team (skills, knowledge, attitudes, structure of the team...) - experience, coachability,*
- *the industry in which the startup operates (AI, digital transformation, IoT, e-commerce, other...) - they stick to their categories*
- *the product/service itself -*
- *potential for growth -*

- potential for profit due to incubation -
- risks (mainly business risks) -
- your strategy -

Are you looking forward to having foreign startups as well?

Yes, from Germany.

GENERAL VIEW/OPINION ON LOCAL ECOSYSTEM:

What are the main differences between this region and the currently well developed regions (startups-wise) and what could be the potential to reach such a level or get closer to them?

They are more collaborative (foreigners). They have a more supportive environment. They are also thinking about more global goals, like sustainability - more social entrepreneurship.

Is there anything (IT talent, funding, etc.) that this ecosystem can offer that is at the same level or even better than the current well developed ones?

IT talent, also that the ecosystem is very open to everyone. The costs are cheaper than in other countries. Governmental: they are supportive.

What are the obstacles for startups with great potential that the system holds in?

Language barrier. And international sales and sales strategy.

What is your experience: Do startups want/willing to open to the EU's/other region's markets?

They are mostly working in EU or US markets. Some of them are in Asia. Depends on their product model.

What are the biggest obstacles?

Language, sales (market fit)

7.6 TRANGELS (TUR)

Name of the interviewee: Hale Umul (angel investor)

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/in/hale-umul-1991832a/>>

Nationality: Turkish

Name of the organization: Trangels <<https://www.trangels.com/>>

EASA: Best Accelerator and Best Newcomer

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/trangels/about/>>

Trangels Financial Services is a „Business and Enterprise“ development company established in Istanbul with the intention of being the most popular and well-known in Turkey, as well as the awareness of the people concerned in the developed and developing countries by the investors.

The purpose of the company; is to support projects that are expected to create significant benefits in the early stages of business, science and technology initiatives and, when supported, in a short time across the country or the world. These projects include inventions, new ideas or new applications. It is aimed to provide entrepreneurs with the resource pool needed in business and finance dimensions, without hindering the independence and innovation characteristics of entrepreneurs, and to bring them to a level where they can continue their business without support.

One of the most important problems in the economy and social life of our country is the inability to complete the work started. Trangels Financial Services Inc.'s founders believe that every idea should be evaluated and brought to a level that will add value to the economy. In order to achieve these goals, every promising idea that will add value to both the economy and social life will be evaluated. It aims to invest in these projects and to help these initiatives grow in line with their goals by using its knowledge and experience.

GENERAL QUESTIONS ABOUT THE CAUCASUS AND CENTRAL-ASIAN REGION

In which regions have you previously invested? And at what stage?

95% of the time invest in early stage startups. – most of them B2B. Less than 1–2 years old, most cases they don't have MVP, maybe a very early prototype. 90% in Turkey

and in companies which are in other countries but they are Turkish originally. Only one investment was in the USA.

How much are you focused on investing in your local ecosystem versus other startup hubs (or everywhere) in general? More than 50%? Less?

90% in Turkey and in companies which are in other countries but they are Turkish originally.

What's your latest, most exciting investment? Why so? Please, explain.

Beginning of autumn, October was the latest. Exciting in biotechnology focusing on agriculture and fresh goods. The other one is clean energy (it was 5 years ago, and was at a very early stage).

Are there any startups that you wish you would see in the industry but you don't? What are some overlooked opportunities right now?

More biotechnology startups - more opportunities, like laboratories for such startups would be good, more startups in education (EdTech) would be welcomed too, and also would be good to have less startups focusing on software.

What are you looking for in your next investment, in general?

The team. Has to be a good and balanced team with different backgrounds and work with harmony. There is no sector focus now, but I don't want to invest now in software, I would like to continue to invest in biotechnology.

Where are you looking for your investment, in general?

90% comes from incubators/accelerators.

Which industry segments that you invest in look weaker or more exposed to potential shifts in consumer and business behavior because of COVID-19? What are the opportunities startups may be able to tap into during these unprecedented times?

None of the sector is invested really, but people get sick from the teams and it affects them anyway. Also travel regulations - they could not work.

What do you think generally about the Caucasus and Central-Asian as a region to invest in? What are the biggest challenges in this region?

Maybe instead of creating incubation programs in every country they should do more Pan-regional work together.

What are the biggest opportunities/potential?

In Turkey, systems to help startups to scale up – finding money for example

Are there enough HUBs, incubators/accelerators working there actively? How are they in your opinion?

There are enough, but need improvement.

What does your local ecosystem need right now the most? What does the region need?

Possible solution – corporations should create more opportunities and could collaborate more with incubators and startups.

What do you think of the Angel, VC culture in the region?

It would be good to have more Angels. There is a gap between angels and VCs. During the scale up process the VCs invest. But in the middle they struggle, they don't need VC money (too big amount) but Angels not enough.

What is the most popular investment stage in the region?

Early mostly in term of number of companies

How could you describe the investor's attitude and behaviour with each other?

Trangels actually do that. They co-invest. There are around 100 investors but around 50 are active investors. No standard way of collaborating between angels. Only one investment done with cooperation with another group.

DETAILS ABOUT INVESTMENT

What is your general investment strategy? The amount of equity (in %) you ask is based on what? What is the general approach? How do you evaluate the worth of startups? Do you ask for voting rights as well? Do you provide "smart-money"?

They don't ask for more than 15%, but more around 8-10-12%. They do a second round of investments as well, but it is based on KPIs. After a KPI is reached they do another round. It is very hard to evaluate the worth of startups.

What is the desired rate of return on investment throughout a given timeframe or over the life cycle of your investment in general?

We haven't made any exits but we sold some shares so far.

In terms of years: 7 years.

How big are the funds (amount of cash)/categories in your region invested in different stages? (in USD)

Idea: USD 100.000

Pre-seed: USD 500.000

What is the situation about „gender-based“ investing (investments supporting female entrepreneurs and founders)? Do you have a female founder in your portfolio currently, or have you had before?

Yes, they have. Actually two biotechnology companies are run by women.

Are you in favour of more social impact focused startups (focusing on sustainability, green technologies, social issues, human rights...etc) than financially interested ones (like fintech, e-commerce..etc)? Why so?

They don't have a sector focus so they invest in social entrepreneurship.

Their business model is weak in a way.

Not too many investors are focusing on them though.

Government funds are still significant in Turkey.

7.7 UKRAINIAN STARTUP FUND (UKR)

Name of the organization: Ukrainian Startup Fund (USF)

<https://usf.com.ua/en/>

Managing director: Pavlo Kartashov

LinkedIn: <https://linkedin.com/in/pavlo-kartashov-0185ba32>

The **Ukrainian Startup Fund** is a state fund launched on the initiative of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. The mission of the fund is to promote the creation and development of technological startups in the early stages (pre-seed and seed), in order to increase their global competitiveness. The process of selecting startups for grants takes place on a competitive basis: companies are evaluated and elected by the board of independent investment experts.

The USF became the largest angel investor in Ukraine in 2020, 80 startups were selected for grant funding worth nearly USD 3 million in 2020. The Fund is a state-owned fund launched on the initiative of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine and Ministry of Finance to promote the development of the Ukrainian startup ecosystem in 2018. The fund has a corporate governance structure and USD 20 million of authorized capital, which is fully available to fund startups.

The sectoral focus is on Tech & innovation, but not limited to a particular field. The investment activities are directed at pre-seed and seed phase startups. They offer non-refundable and non-equity grants for these companies. USF also funds grants for startups on acceleration programs.

Are you looking forward to having foreign startups as well? Have you had any before? Are you currently having? From which country?

Within our vision and goal we support only Ukrainian businesses. It may be foreign founders of the startups though, but it's supposed to be a lawful Ukrainian legal entity.

What does your mentor pool look like? Where are your mentors coming from?

Our experts: from Corporate environment; VCs, Angels; Founders of startups; accelerators, local business representatives.

What else do you provide apart from know-how and network? Are you investing in your own startups? Maybe co-investing?

We are planning to launch co-financing opportunities for startups in 2021. The startup co-financing program allows venture funds, private investors and corporate funds to invest in startups together with the Fund. (co-funding).

How much do you usually invest?

We offer 2 types of grants: USD 25k on pre-seed stage and USD 50k on seed.

How much equity do you usually ask for?

Funds don't participate in equity.

GENERAL VIEW/OPINION ON LOCAL ECOSYSTEM:

What are the main differences between this region and the currently well developed (startups-wise) regions and what could be the potential to reach such a level or get closer to them?

More than 200k tech specialists (20% average annual growth), venture capital potential, central geo location in Europe.

Is there anything (IT talent, funding, etc.) that this ecosystem can offer that is at the same level or even better than the current well developed ones?

1) IT talent, human capital, talented and highly-educated workforce; 2) a long tradition of research in science and technology; 3) a successful and growing information technology (IT) Industry; 4) growing access to markets in Europe.

What are the obstacles for startups with great potential that the system holds in?

Lack of early-stage funding (lack of support), lack of venture capital, imperfections of legislation,

Need to develop critical business skills (how to develop a globally-competitive business model).

What is your opinion on education (startup-wise)?

Education is crucial for the development of startups. We launched the acceleration program in 2020 and are going to fund startups with a grant (up to USD 10k) on acceleration programs.

What and how do you contribute to the development of it?

The launch of the USF Acceleration program will give an opportunity to get business knowledge from the best accelerators from the market.

How do you see universities doing in this field? Are they active?

Incubator YEP! (our partner) is building an ecosystem of youth entrepreneurship in Ukraine and Eastern Europe, which provides students in universities with opportunities for personal and professional development through entrepreneurship. The goal is to boost university entrepreneurship in Ukraine to the new level and create a strong trend among youth to make startups.

Do you know any other platform/initiation, maybe on governmental level?

There are several government agencies in Ukraine that support entrepreneurs.

What is your experience: do startups want/willing to open to the EU's/other region's markets?

Yes, our startups have global orientation and potential in scaling.

Specifically, what part of the world?

Central Europe, USA, England, Middle East.

Specifically, which part of the EU/which countries?

Central Europe

What are the biggest obstacles?

Limited access and lack of support, legal and fiscal obstacles.

How can you help them?

Give them opportunities to grow in Ukraine first.

Do you have any connection with EU/or other regional HUBs, incubators, accelerators?

Yes, USF works closely with international accelerators such as Blue Lake Accelerator, Seedstars, 500 startups, USMAC, Startup Wise Guys, etc.

What are the tangible results of such cooperation?

Accredited acceleration programs for the startups, networking and access to additional financing opportunities.

7.8 YEP! (UKR)

Name of the interviewee: Andriy Zaikin (Founder & CEO)

LinkedIn: <<https://linkedin.com/in/andriy-zaikin-07327a38>>

Nationality: Ukrainian

Name of the organization: YEP! Startup Incubators

LinkedIn: <<https://www.linkedin.com/company/yep-startup-incubators/about/>>

YEP is a network of academic business-incubators. We provide a business-related education for youth, contributing to the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of Ukraine.

Mission of the YEP:

- to build a powerful ecosystem for the development of youth entrepreneurship in Ukraine,
- to form a partnership between the state, science, business, venture funds, education and expert environment,
- to introduce entrepreneurship training into all Ukrainian universities.

They have an incubation program for students and now they are managing 20 startups in 6 semesters. The startups who are willing to work furthermore are invited to their accelerator programme where they can work together.

The main goal is to put them to the market and to make them ready for 1st investment. They launched an official course at universities called: Innovative Entrepreneurship and Startup Management. YEP does not apply any access filter, it receives startups from any area.

Currently 64 universities are involved in their curriculum with more than 100 teachers & 300 students. YEP plans to reach 1,000 students/semester. After Demo Day YEP invites investors as well to offer networking possibilities.

What is the most common field they are coming from (AI, Edutech, IoT, e-commerce, digital transformation, others...)

10 batches which means around 250 startups so far who entered the program and 145 who pitched on Demo Day. Now they have around 20 in their programme in different stages.

From what stage are you accepting startups to join?

We start from the idea stage. But now we accept more adult people as well with ideas. We accept startups with MVP and products.

What is the general selection process of the applicants for your program? Which factors are the most relevant to the selection? Please, list 3 or 5 of them in order of importance!

We have a selection process: we collect application forms (100-150) and then we choose around 20-30 for the incubation. Then till the end (Demo Day) we will have 50.

Do you recognize any differences between the local ones and the foreign ones? If yes, then what do you think? What can be the reasons?

First step would be to grow the cultural aspect (entrepreneurship) in universities and middle schools,

Secondly, improve the ecosystem - access to early funds.

What is your experience: Do startups want/willing to open to the EU's/other region's markets?

YEP targets EU markets. It is okay for us if startups focus on the Ukraine market but we try to teach them to think big in the international context.

What are the biggest obstacles?

- *Probably target audience definition - the solution they are creating doesn't match the target group (market fit problems),*
- *Not correct evaluation of market evaluation,*
- *Language barriers.*

Do you have any connection with the EU/or other regional HUBs, incubators, accelerators?

- *Estonia – University of Tartu: 3-4 incubation batch - they have speakers, mentors from there*
- *Startup Amsterdam: couple of workshops,*
- *USA – North Carolina University.*

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

SUMMARY

SUMMARY

We see huge potential in the region analyzed. The preconditions for development and progress of startups and their ecosystems are partially at hand, and a modern entrepreneurial culture which can contribute to the success of the whole system is also available. Of course, there are lots of challenges to be solved, but an intelligent, considered digital specialization can be very promising, profitable and fruitful.

One of the goal for MeOut Group is to promote this region as an emerging one, and shed light on its strengths and yet undiscovered opportunities in order to foster cooperation.

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

CONTRIBUTORS

CONTRIBUTORS

Hereby, we would like to thank all the contributors and startups!

OUR MAIN PROFESSIONAL CONTRIBUTORS

Zaur Alakbarov – IBA Innovation Center adviser to CEO of The International Bank of Azerbaijan (Azerbaijan)
Homepage: <https://www.ibar.az/en>

Generations – corporate accelerator (Russia)
Homepage: <https://en.generation-startup.ru/>

Jena Klepa – Open Data incubator (CEO)
Homepage: <http://1991.vc/en/main-page/>

Olesya Kostrykina (Russia)
LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/kostrykinao/>

Yuri Kozik (Ukraine) Advisera (CEO)
Homepage: <https://advisera.org/>

Dmitry Kurin – MTS Startup Hub (Russia)
Homepage: <https://startup.mts.ru/>

Yerjan Ryskali – Clockster (Kazakhstan)
Homepage: <https://clockster.com/>

Ukrainian Startup Fund (USF) (Ukraine)
Homepage: <https://usf.com.ua/en/#usf-sc-2>

Hale Umul – Trangels (Turkey)
Homepage: <https://www.trangels.com/>

Andriy Zaikin – YEP (Ukraine)
Homepage: <https://www.yepworld.org/en/>

**RISING INNOVATION &
EMERGING TALENTS**

**FROM
THE
EAST**

REFERENCES

REFERENCES

1. ADB (2020): Republic of Azerbaijan: Fostering Development of Local Tech Startups. Asian Development Bank. Technical Assistance Report Project Number: 53416-001 Knowledge and Support Technical Assistance (KSTA)

<https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/project-documents/53416/53416-001-tar-en.pdf>

2. BBWA (2019): *The cities that attract Europe's most successful startups.*

<https://www.bbva.com/en/the-cities-that-attract-europes-most-successful-startups/>

3. Bone, J.; Gonzalez-Uribe, J.; Haley, C.; Lahr, H. (2019): *The impact of business accelerators and incubators in the UK – A report on the impact of incubators and accelerators on start-up businesses and on the wider business ecosystem.* Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-impact-of-business-accelerators-and-incubators-in-the-uk>

4. Catalyst Foundation (2019): Tech and Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Mapping.

<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Tech-and-Entrepreneurial-Ecosystem-Mapping-web.pdf>

5. Choladze, D. (2020): Startup Ecosystem Summary – Country Guide Georgia. Startup Universal.

<https://startupuniversal.com/country/georgia/>

6. CIVITTA (2021): Belarus Startup Report – Report for 2020. CIVITTA: The Challenger Advisory

<https://civitta.com/articles/civitta-together-with-bulba-ventures-released-the-third-overview-of-the-startup-ecosystem-of-belarus>

7. Colombelli, A.; Krafft, J.; Vivarelli, M. (2016): *To Be Born Is Not Enough: The Key Role of Innovative Startups*. Forschungsinstitut zur Zukunft der Arbeit/Institute for the Study of Labor, IZA Discussion Paper Series, IZA DP No. 9733.

<http://ftp.iza.org/dp9733.pdf>

8. Corl, E. (2019): *How Startups Drive the Economy*. Medium.com.

<https://medium.com/@ericcorl/how-startups-drive-the-economy-69b73cfbae1>

9. Cukier, D.; Kon, F. (2018): A maturity model for software startup ecosystems. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 7 (1): 1–32.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-018-0091-6>

10. Daily Sabah (2021): Turkey rolls out strategic artificial intelligence road map.

<https://www.dailysabah.com/business/tech/turkey-rolls-out-strategic-artificial-intelligence-road-map>

11. Darkhan, S. (2020): Startup Ecosystem in Kazakhstan.

https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/startup-ecosystems-kazakhstan-seitkazin-darkhan/?trk=public_profile_article_view

12. Darpass (2020): Armenian Startup Ecosystem | VCs, Angels and Startup Programs. Darpass Insight.

<https://darpass.com/blog/2020/12/16/armenian-startup-ecosystem-vcs-angels-and-startup-programs/>

13. Davtyan, M. (2021): Startup Ecosystem Or Armenia As The World's Next Technological Hub. I-AM.AM First Global Armenian Directory.

<https://i-am.am/startup-ecosystem-or-armenia-as-the-worlds-next-technological-hub/>

14. dealroom.co (2020): Consortium of Ukraine's leading ecosystem players team up to launch startup database, led by ICU, powered by Dealroom. [Dealroom.co](https://dealroom.co/blog/consortium-ukraines-leading-ecosystem-players-launch-startup-database) blog.

<https://dealroom.co/blog/consortium-ukraines-leading-ecosystem-players-launch-startup-database>

15. Deloitte (2020): *Productivity is not an accident – The economics and impact of Victoria’s startup ecosystem.*

<https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/au/Documents/Economics/deloitte-au-economics-productivity-is-not-an-accident-020620.pdf>

16. Dodd, J. (2021): Kazakhstan’s established innovation ecosystem leads to thriving startup scene. STARTUPS Magazine.

<https://startups magazine.co.uk/article-kazakhstans-established-innovation-ecosystem-leads-thriving-startup-scene>

17. Dutta, S.; Lanvin, B.; Wunsch-Vincent, S. (2020): Global Innovation Index 2020 – Who will finance innovation? 13th Edition. Cornell University, INSEAD, World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). ISBN 978-2-38192-000-9

<https://www.globalinnovationindex.org/Home>

18. enpact (2019): Startup Ecosystem Report – Tashkent. enpact e.V. data lab – Berlin, Germany. ISBN 978-3-96604-008-2.

<https://www.enpact.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/startup-ecosystem-report-tashkent-uzbekistan.pdf>

19. Entrepreneur HK (2014): Why is Kazakhstan Lacking a Healthy Startup Ecosystem? Entrepreneur Hong Kong.

<https://entrepreneurhk.org/why-is-kazakhstan-lacking-a-healthy-startup-ecosystem/>

20. European Commission, Kantor Management Consultants (2018): ICT Innovation and Start-up Ecosystems – Study Report. HiQSTEP Project.

<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/3.ICT-innovation-and-start-up-ecosystems.pdf>

21. EU4Digital (2020): New organisational forms in support of ICT innovation: policy recommendations: Azerbaijan.

<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Policy-recommendation-for-Azerbaijan-in-the-area-of-New-organisational-forms-in-support-of-ICT-innovation.pdf>

22. EU4Digital (2021): Guide for building the ICT entrepreneurial ecosystems in the Eastern partner countries: Maturity analysis and recommendations – Final Report.

<<https://eufordigital.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Guide-for-building-the-ICT-entrepreneurial-ecosystems-in-the-Eastern-partner-countries-maturity-analysis-and-recommendations.pdf>>

23. Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation (2016): *The economic impact of high-growth startups*.

<https://www.kauffman.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/PD_HighGrowth060716.pdf>

24. EY, USAID (2021): National Strategy to Increase Foreign Direct Investment in Ukraine. Ernst & Young, United States Agency for International Development.

<<https://ukraineinvest.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/FDI-Strategy-Section-2-Digital-Infrastructure-ENG.pdf>>

25. Fitz, M. (2021): 9 Top Azerbaijan Apps Companies and Startups of 2021. BestStartup. Asia

<<https://beststartup.asia/9-top-azerbaijan-apps-companies-and-startups-of-2021/>>

26. Fybish, A. (2021): Top Russian Startups To Watch in 2021. Startup Stash.

<<https://startupstash.com/russian-startups/>>

27. Gasanova, M. (2020): Georgian Startups Rankings with the Volume of Attracted Investments. Forbes Georgia.

<<https://forbes.ge/georgian-startups-rankings-with-the-volume-of-attracted-investments/>>

28. GITA (2021): Startup Ecosystem. Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency.

<<https://gita.gov.ge/eng>>

29. Hazell, N. (2017): *Changing the face of start-ups: Why diversity is not a nice-to-have but a must-have*. OECD.org topics.

<<http://www.oecd.org/innovation/changing-the-face-of-start-ups-why-diversity-is-not-a-nice-to-have-but-a-must-have.htm>>

30. Isenberg, D.; Fabre, F. (2014): *Don't Judge the Economy by the Number of Start-Ups*. HBR.org – Harvard Business Review.

<https://hbr.org/2014/10/dont-judge-the-economy-by-the-number-of-start-ups>

31. Investopress (2019): Azerbaijan ranks as 3rd best CIS country for startups. Investopress.com.

<https://investopress.com/azerbaijan-startups>

32. Kayahan, D. (2020): Challenges and Opportunities of Developing Startup Ecosystems: Central and Eastern Europe and Turkey Example. Medium.com

<https://medium.com/startup-intellect/challenges-and-opportunities-of-developing-startup-ecosystems-central-and-eastern-europe-and-759f77a0b1aa>

33. KG Labs Public Foundation (2021): Kyrgyzstan Startup Ecosystem.

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/ixte_QrMvfHGxUAncbRpIL9_JUL17aGrqg_HyjBBOfRE/edit#gid=361801725

34. Khoshimov, E.; Makhmudaliyev, F. (2020): Digital Transformation of Corporate Governance in Uzbekistan: Current State, Challenges and Perspectives. *International Finance and Accounting*, Vol. 2020: No. 6, Article 30.

<https://uzjournals.edu.uz/inter=nance/vol2020/iss6/30>

35. KPMG (2021): Turkish Startup Investments Review – Q2 2021. KPMG Turkey & 212.vc

<https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/tr/pdf/2021/08/turkish-startup-investments-q2-2021.pdf>

36. Lanvin, B.; Monteiro, F. (2020): The Global Talent Competitiveness Index – Global Talent in the Age of Artificial Intelligence. INSEAD, the Adecco Group, and Google Inc. ISBN: 979-10-95870-19-7

<https://www.insead.edu/sites/default/files/assets/dept/globalindices/docs/GTCI-2020-report.pdf>

37. Moore, J. F. (1993): Predators and prey: a new ecology of competition. *Harvard Business Review*, 71 (3): 75–83.

38. Nagy S. (2020): Az agrár startup ökoszisztémák sikerességének összetevői. In: Kis K.; Komarek L.; Monostori T. (szerk.): *Mezőgazdasági és vidékfejlesztési kutatások a jövő szolgálatában*. MTA SZAB Mezőgazdasági Szakbizottság, Szeged. (2020): 23–38.

39. Nagy S., Gulyás L. (2015): Számvevőszéki értékteremtés „turbulens” környezetben – a komplexitás kezelésének lehetőségei. *Vezetéstudomány*, 46 (7): 2–14.

40. OC&C (2018): Tech Entrepreneurship Ecosystem in the Russian Federation. OC&C Strategy Consultants.

https://www.occstrategy.com/media/1311/tech-eship-ecosystem-in-focus-countries_russia.pdf

41. Orlova, M. (2021): First State Innovation Center opened in Kyrgyzstan. 24.KG News Agency.

https://24.kg/english/211873_First_State_Innovation_Center_opened_in_Kyrgyzstan/

42. Peak.kg (2020): Fanki: Startup from Kyrgyzstan in Top-25 of the Entrepreneurship World Cup 2020. [Peak.kg](https://peak.kg) Success Stories.

<https://peak.kg/en/fanki-startup-from-kyrgyzstan-in-top-25-of-the-entrepreneurship-world-cup-2020/>

43. Porter, M. E. (2011): *Competitive advantage of nations: creating and sustaining superior performance*. Simon and Schuster. ISBN 9781451651492

44. Ritchie, B.; Swisher, N. (2018): *The Big Small: The Economic Benefits of Startups*. University of Notre Dame.

<https://ideacenter.nd.edu/news-events/news/the-big-small-the-economic-benefits-of-startups/>

45. Schumpeter, J. A. (1934): *The Theory of Economic Development – An Inquiry into Profits, Capital, Credit, Interest, and the Business Cycle*. Harvard Economic Studies 46.

46. Seedstars Global (2021): These Startups Are Going to Make You Think Twice About Moldova.

<https://www.seedstars.com/content-hub/life/these-startups-are-going-make-you-think-twice-about-moldova/>

47. Seedtable (2021a): 98 Belarus Startups to Watch in 2021.

<https://www.seedtable.com/startups-belarus>

48. Seedtable (2021b): 108 Turkey Startups to Watch in 2021.

<https://www.seedtable.com/startups-turkey>

49. Snow, A. (2017): Turkey's Technology Startups: U.S.–Turkey Collaboration in a Growing Ecosystem. Turkish Heritage Organization – Technology Brief No.1.

<https://www.turkheritage.org/en/publications/factsheets/issue-briefs/turkeys-technology-startups-us-turkey-collaboration-in-a-growing-ecosystem-4676>

50. StartupBlink (2021a): Global Map – Kazakhstan.

<https://www.startupblink.com/startups/kazakhstan>

51. StartupBlink (2021b): Global Map – Accelerators in Ukraine.

<https://www.startupblink.com/accelerators/ukraine>

52. StartupBlink (2021c): Global Map – Ukraine.

<https://www.startupblink.com/startups/ukraine>

53. StartupBlink (2021d): Global Map – Uzbekistan.

<https://www.startupblink.com/startups/uzbekistan>

54. Startupcentraleurasia.com (2021): Startup Ecosystem of Kyrgyzstan – Mini-Research.

<https://www.startupcentraleurasia.com/uploads/other/2021-06/%E1%83%A7%E1%83%98%E1%83%A0%E1%83%92%E1%83%98%E1%83%96%E1%83%94%E1%83%97%E1%83%98.pdf>

55. Startup Europe Partnership (2018): *Startup City Hubs in Europe*.

https://startupeuropepartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/MTB_StartupCityHubsInEurope.pdf

56. Startup Genome (2019): *Can Culture Be Counted? Why Local Connectedness Matters for your Startup.*

<https://startupgenome.com/blog/can-culture-be-counted-why-local-connectedness-matters-for-your-startup>

57. Startup Genome (2020): *The Global Startup Ecosystem Report, GSER 2020 – The New Normal for the Global Startup Economy and the Impact of COVID-19.* Crunchbase and Startup Genome.

<https://startupgenome.com/report/gser2020>

58. Startup Genome (2021): *Moldova – startup ecosystem.*

<https://startupgenome.com/ecosystems/moldova>

59. Startups & Places (2019): *SHM 2019: City Rankings.* The Official Startup Heatmap Europe Blog.

<https://startupsandplaces.com/shm2019-startup-highways-part-iv/>

60. Startup Ranking (2021a): *Top Startups – Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan.*

<https://www.startupranking.com/top/bishkek>

61. Startup Ranking (2021b): *Top Startups – Tbilisi, Georgia.*

<https://www.startupranking.com/top/tbilisi>

62. Startups Watch, Turkey Investment Office (2021): *The State of Turkish Startup Ecosystem. An In-Depth Analysis and Evaluation.* Startups Watch & Presidency of the Republic of Turkey Investment Office.

<https://www.invest.gov.tr/en/library/publications/lists/investpublications/the-state-of-turkish-startup-ecosystem.pdf>

63. Tech Ukraine (2021): *360 Tech Ecosystem Overview – Deep dive into the 360 Tech Ecosystem Overview.*

<https://techukraine.org/360-%d1%82%d0%b5%d1%81h-ecosystem-overview/>

64. TUZ Ventures, AIFC (2021): The Startup Ecosystem of Kazakhstan. TUZ Ventures & AIFC Astana International Financial Centre.

<https://tech.aifc.kz/files/pages/2024/documents/14/kz-report-july-2021-1.pdf>

65. TUZ Ventures, IT Park (2021): The Startup Ecosystem of Uzbekistan. April 2021 Report.

<https://img1.wsimg.com/blobby/go/15667cfc-6d6f-4e91-81a4-ac4243dea7c8/downloads/Uzbek%20Report%20Design%20apr15.pdf?ver=1624459228671>

66. UkraineInvest (2021): UkraineInvest Guide – Explore Your Opportunities.

<https://ukraineinvest.gov.ua/guide/>

67. Ukraine Now (2021): Startup Ecosystem.

<https://ukraine.ua/invest-trade/startup-ecosystem-ukraine/>

68. UNECE (2021): A Roadmap to develop the innovation ecosystem of Kyrgyzstan. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe.

<https://unece.org/economic-cooperation-and-integration/news/roadmap-develop-innovation-ecosystem-kyrgyzstan>

69. UNIDO (2020): The Innovation Ecosystem of Moldova. Report prepared under UNIDO Country Programme for Moldova 2019–2023. UNIDO – United Nations Industrial Development Organization.

https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/files/2021-02/Report_on_Innovation_Ecosystem_of_Moldova.pdf

70. Ünsal, S. (2020): Turkish Startup Ecosystem Map [v6.0]. startups.watch (SW)

<https://blog.startups.watch/turkish-startup-ecosystem-map-v6-0-ea9f21362917>

71. USAID, Belbiz Group (2021): Bad Year – Belarus Startups 2020.

https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00XDKJ.pdf

72. USF (2019): Strategic vision 2020–2025. Ukrainian Startup Fund.

https://usf.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/strategy_usf_2020-2025.pdf

73. Walkers, P. J. (2021): Azerbaijan launches accelerator for startups targeting European markets. CoFounder – cofmag.com.

<https://www.cofmag.com/2021/09/azerbaijan-launches-accelerator-for-startups-targeting-european-markets/>

74. Westlund, H.; Olsson, A. R. (2011): *Economic Entrepreneurship, Startups and Their Effects on Local Development: The Case of Sweden.*

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254457482_Economic_Entrepreneurship_Startups_and_Their_Effects_on_Local_Development_The_Case_of_Sweden

75. World Bank (2021): Research and development expenditure (% of GDP) – Azerbaijan.

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/GB.XPD.RSDV.GD.ZS?locations=AZ>

76. Wu, J.; Atkinson, R. D. (2017): *How Technology-Based Start-Ups Support U.S. Economic Growth.* ITIF – Information Technology & Innovation Foundation.

<https://itif.org/publications/2017/11/28/how-technology-based-start-ups-support-us-economic-growth>

77. Yushkevich, N. (2019a): The startup ecosystem of Armenia. Startup Jedi.

<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-armenia>

78. Yushkevich, N. (2019b): The startup ecosystem of Georgia. Startup Jedi.

<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-georgia>

79. Yushkevich, N. (2020a): The startup ecosystem of Belarus. Startup Jedi.

<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-belarus>

80. Yushkevich, N. (2020b): The startup ecosystem of Russia. Startup Jedi.

<https://startupjedi.vc/content/startup-ecosystem-russia>

Bem mentris. Sat. Sero vilicesto ales Marbit, quite elium iaequam dem octa, vivide cribunte mus fur. Id isquidii ste nocribustra ductandem audeps, o esil horum in nondi, C. Vivivivendii iuroriptiae ego vis. Tiquo caet? in num, meis publia?